

BACHELOR INFORMATICA

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Decision support for effectively selecting a study programme

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Abstract

High dropout rates in study programmes for the information sciences negatively impact society and students' lives. The European Union has a large shortage of skilled ICT workers and in the Netherlands, the average student's debt is nearly 20,000 euros. At the University of Amsterdam, the College of Informatics is experiencing above-average dropout rates. This is suspected to be caused by gaps in the information available to high school students and an unclear distinction between the three bachelor's degrees offered by the College of Informatics. In an effort to decrease these dropout rates, this thesis proposes an interactive decision support tool that can be used to support prospective students in selecting one of these three programmes. The tool uses a profile of current students to evaluate the performance of each study programme on a set of selection criteria and uses these evaluations to create a personalized ranking of the programmes. To this end, Profile Aware Pair-wise Additive Weighting (PAW-PAW) is introduced, a decision-making method that combines aspects of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) with the weighted sum method (WSM). An implementation of this method is compared to a decision tree based decision support system and a conversational system based on the GPT 3.5 language model. While participants occasionally perceived PAW-PAW's interactions as overwhelming, they preferred it over the decision tree, which most users found too rigid, and the conversational system, which had a tendency to stray off-topic and hallucinate incorrect information. PAW-PAW outperformed the other systems on two out of four KPIs, and 60% of the participants indicated that they were more likely to use PAW-PAW when selecting a study program than the other two systems. Insights from the participants' feedback, however, indicate that each system has its benefits, and that each system may perform best at different stages of the study programme selection process. As such, we conclude that supporting students in study programme selection would probably be most successfully done by a combination of decision support systems.

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Introduction

1.1 Context

In the year preceding their graduation, Dutch high school students go through the process of selecting a study programme for their tertiary education. In a country where the average student's debt is 18200 euros (*Studieschulden 2011-2022* 2022), this is no small task. Enrolling in a study programme that is not right for them may not only negatively impact their enjoyment of their education, but also increase their chances of dropping out early or taking longer than the designated time to graduate. This may pose problems to the student personally and to society as a whole.

Dropouts impact society, both in business and government spending. The European Union has a shortage of ICT workers, with 55% of enterprises having hard-to-fill vacancies for ICT specialists in 2020 (*ICT specialists - statistics on hard-to-fill vacancies in enterprises* 2021). Preventing dropouts from study programmes in the field of information technology could prove an important step toward decreasing this shortage. Furthermore, in 2015, the Dutch government spent 40700 euros per bachelor's degree given out by Dutch universities¹ (*Gediplomeerden en afgestudeerden; onderwijssoort, vanaf 1900* 2022; *Onderwijsuitgaven per einddiploma; gemiddelde route 1998-2015* 2016; *Overheid; uitgaven aan onderwijs en studietoelagen vanaf 1900* 2022), amounting to 28.9% of government spending on scientific education (*WO*) in that year. Improving dropout rates could decrease the cost per degree, thus increasing the funds left for other expenses.

For students, dropping out or taking longer to graduate may result in wasted time and effort, and in some cases thousands of euros in unnecessary student debt. Furthermore, selecting the right study programme may result in higher student engagement, which is positively correlated to student wellbeing (Boulton et al. 2019). Since the proportion of mentally unhealthy people between the ages of 16 and 20 has increased from 12.0% in 2020 to 20.6% in 2021 in the Netherlands (*Gezondheid en zorggebruik; persoonskenmerken, 2014-2021* 2022), increasing student wellbeing should be of high priority.

Students may have many reasons for enrolling in a study programme, and reasons for dropping out vary wildly. However, research shows that some reasons are more common than others. Kori et al. 2016 found that *intrinsic motivation* (i.e. interest in the field, the wish to develop their skills in the field, and the belief that the field is important to society) is an important factor for not only students' decision to enrol in a computer science program, but also for students' decision to stay enrolled or re-enrol when they have already started the program. Since this intrinsic motivation has a positive effect on student retention, ensuring a realistic view of the field and providing assistance in study programme selection before enrolment would likely have a positive impact on dropout rates.

¹Note that the Dutch definition of a university is used here. The numbers referenced in this paragraph apply only to *WO* (*Wetenschappelijk Onderwijs*, Scientific Education), thus excluding *HBO* (*Hoger Beroepsonderwijs*, Higher Professional Education).

One way to support students in study programme selection would be through a decision support system (*DSS*). Decision support systems are software systems meant to support a decision maker without deciding for them. These types of systems have been successfully applied in management, government, education, healthcare, and military (Eom and Kim 2006). In education, decision support systems have seen a multitude of applications. Some application focus on decisions made in the organization of tertiary education, such as study programme activity selection (Puspitasari, Wijaya, and Mentari 2020) and selecting students for scholarships (Utami and Ruskan 2020). Other applications concern decisions made by the students, such as selecting a topic for a thesis (Daniati and Nugroho 2016) or creating a personalized ranking of universities (Giannoulis and Ishizaka 2010).

These applications of DSS give the impression that such a system could be used to assist in study programme selection. However, research on that application is lacking in several areas. For example, Ariani and Endra 2013 implemented a DSS for study programme selection. In this implementation, the input variables consisted of the results of an interview, grades for two courses, and the score on a test. As such, this system would not be able to support the decision of students with no prior contact with informatics. Similar gaps are present in other studies on similar applications.

As will be discussed in section 2.1.1, students who have enrolled in a program will use the information that became available through experience to re-evaluate and possibly change their decision (El Nemar, Vrontis, and Thrassou 2020). Thus, prospective students may benefit from information on the experiences of students that came before them. This information is especially useful if the current and prospective students have matching profiles, as this would allow the decision support to be personalized to some degree.

1.2 Research question

At the University of Amsterdam (*UvA*), the College of Informatics (*CoI*) is experiencing dropouts among students in the first semester of their bachelor programs. Figure 1.1 shows that these dropout rates are higher than the average of all study programmes at the University of Amsterdam's Faculty of Science (*FNWI*). Furthermore, with an average dropout rate of 42.3% between 2003/'04 and 2022/'23, CoI is experiencing significantly more dropouts than the European Union, where the dropout rate among computer science students was estimated to be around 19% by Hüsing et al. 2013. Suspicions are that these dropouts can partially be explained by:

1. Gaps in the information provided to high school students in the process of selecting a study programme, and
2. An unclear (to high school students) distinction between the three bachelor's programs offered by the College of Informatics, namely B.Sc. Informatica (computing science), B.Sc. Informatiekunde (information science) and B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie (artificial intelligence) (Z. Zhao, personal communication, April 4, 2023).

This project aims to interpret the dropouts at CoI and propose a possible solution. Using the College of Informatics as a case study, the following question will be answered:

RQ : How can we support students in their decision on which study programme to enrol in?

To understand how prospective students can be supported in their decision, information on the experiences of current students in the study programmes is needed. This information could be used to match a student's interests and motivations to one of the study programmes. Furthermore, there is a need to understand in what way a decision support tool would fit into the study programme selection process. To this end, a model of the decision-making process should be created. Thus, to answer the research question, the following sub-questions should be answered.

SQ₁ : How can a student's background be profiled?

SQ₂ : How can a student's decision-making process be modelled?

Figure 1.1: The dropout rates of the study programmes of the College of Informatics (*CoI*) compared to the dropout rates of all study programmes at the Faculty of Science (*FNWI*) at University of Amsterdam, plotted against the first academic year in which the students were enrolled. The data was gathered on April 24, 2023. The dip at the far right of the graph may be explained by the fact that the academic year 22/23 has not yet ended. The average dropout rate from 03/04 to 22/23 was 42.3% at CoI, which is higher than the average at FNWI (39.1%) (Krakers 2023) and the average of the European Union (estimated 19% by Hüsing et al. 2013).

SQ₃ : How can an interactive decision support system for study programme selection that considers a student’s background be prototyped?

1.3 Contributions

This study will contribute to a better understanding of decision support systems and the study programme selection process. Chapter 2 presents a literature study on the relevant theory on decision-making, student retention, and established decision-making techniques. Furthermore, it provides a description of related studies and an analysis of gaps in the information available on the subject. To understand how this knowledge can be used to prototype a DSS for study programme selection, a profile of current students at CoI will be created, and prospective students’ decision-making process will be modelled. This information will be used to design and implement a prototype of a decision support system for study programme selection at CoI. Finally, the effectiveness of the prototype will be tested and compared to two other DSS on several criteria.

State of the Art and Problem Analysis

2.1 Theoretical framework

2.1.1 The decision-making process

Deciding on a study programme and educational institution to enrol in is a largely rational process. The decision maker gathers information, weighs the available knowledge against their wants, needs, and values, and chooses the option that appears optimal to them (Z. Milojevic and Ž. Milojevic 2015). It does, however, not fit into the *rational model* of decision-making processes; instead, the *bounded rationality model* is more applicable (Lunenburg 2010). In the rational model, the decision is made under certainty; the decider knows their alternatives, outcomes, and decision criteria, and can make the optimal decision and implement it. The bounded rationality model, however, applies to more uncertain scenarios, where

- the decision will be based on an incomplete understanding of the nature of the problem,
- decision makers are unable to generate all possible solutions for consideration,
- it is impossible to predict all possible outcomes for each alternative,
- it is impossible to determine which alternative is optimal.

This uncertainty was demonstrated to be present in the study programme selection process by El Nemar, Vrontis, and Thrassou 2020; they found that a part of the information required to select the best study programme is found through experience, and as such becomes available only after the student has already enrolled into a study programme.

The bounded rationality model has several biases to look out for. The *recency effect*, for example, causes information found later in the process to be of greater influence on the decision than the information that was found earlier. Conversely, the *primacy effect* may cause information found early in the process to disproportionately impact the decision. The decision may also be influenced by a preference the decision maker may already have before gathering the relevant information. This may cause them to *bolster the alternative*, accepting only information that supports their preference and dismissing other information as illegitimate, unimportant, or otherwise unacceptable. Finally, when presented with complex and uncertain situations, some decision makers base their decision on intuition or rules of thumb, while others may be prone to *satisficing*; accepting the first alternative that satisfies minimal standards without considering further alternatives (Lunenburg 2010).

Selecting a tertiary education institution is a process that takes place in three stages, during all of which information is gathered continuously. The three stages are:

1. Need recognition,
2. Evaluation of tertiary institutions,

3. Tertiary institution choice and enrolment.

During these stages, several factors influence the students' decision process. In the first stage, the main influences are parents, friends, teachers, websites, social media, and published information. In the second stage, university marketing and recruitment activities, university staff, and current and graduate students are added to that list. In the final stage, the influences consist of the satisfaction levels of current and graduate students, parents, friends, admissions, and social media (El Nemar, Vrontis, and Thrassou 2020).

2.1.2 Decision-making techniques

In situations where a decision maker is aware that they have trouble weighing the available information objectively, they may apply techniques that assist them in making the decision. This section presents a selection of decision-making techniques that can be applied in a digital decision support system and show promise in the field of education.

Weighted Sum Method (WSM)

The Weighted Sum Method (*WSM*), also known as Simple Additive Weighting (*SAW*), is one of the most commonly used decision techniques (Odu 2019). With WSM, each of the n criteria for the decision is assigned a relative weight w_j , and each alternative i is given a score x_{ij} on each criterion j . The total performance of each alternative is then calculated with

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_{ij}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (2.1)$$

creating a ranking where the alternative with the highest performance S_i is ranked best (Wang et al. 2009).

Weighted Product Method (WPM)

The Weighted Product Method (*WPM*) is a method that was proposed as an improvement on WSM, and as such, follows similar concepts (Odu 2019). In WPM, each of the m alternatives is also assigned a score x_{ij} on each criterion j , and each criterion is assigned a weight w_j . However, the calculation of the total score for an alternative is different from WSM:

$$S_i = \prod_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^{w_j}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (2.2)$$

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The Analytical Hierarchy Process (*AHP*) was first proposed by Saaty 1977, who used school selection as one of the first examples to demonstrate the technique. In the past few decades, AHP has become an increasingly popular technique to make multi-criteria decisions. In AHP, alternatives are ranked by making pair-wise comparisons of criteria and alternatives. Each pair of criteria A_i and A_j is assigned a score of 1 to 9, where 9 means criterion A_i severely outweighs criterion A_j , and 1 means the two criteria are weighted equally. This score is treated as an estimator for the ratio between the weights of the two criteria $\frac{w_i}{w_j}$. The relative weight of each criterion is found by entering the values for $\frac{w_i}{w_j}$ into the matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{w_1}{w_1} & \frac{w_1}{w_2} & \dots & \frac{w_1}{w_n} \\ \frac{w_2}{w_1} & \frac{w_2}{w_2} & \dots & \frac{w_2}{w_n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{w_n}{w_1} & \frac{w_n}{w_2} & \dots & \frac{w_n}{w_n} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.3)$$

One of the eigenvectors \vec{v}_A of matrix A contains the relative weights of all criteria, and is found using

$$A\vec{v}_A = \lambda_{max}\vec{v}_A, \quad (2.4)$$

where λ_{max} is the eigenvalue of matrix A with the largest modulus. Since all of A 's entries are positive, this eigenvalue is guaranteed to be a real positive number.

The comparisons may be performed inconsistently. For example, the decision maker could decide a to be more important than b , and b to be more important than c , while also indicating that c is more important than a . Although it is still possible to generate an outcome despite such inconsistencies, Saaty 1977 states that these inconsistencies can be detected. If matrix A is consistent, its largest eigenvalue should be close or equal to the number of criteria n .

Similar matrices are produced through pair-wise comparisons between all m alternatives on each of the n criteria. The eigenvectors of all $n \ m \times m$ matrices that result from these comparisons denote the score for each alternative on each of the criteria. The matrix of the scores can then be found by

$$S = [\vec{v}_1 \quad \vec{v}_2 \quad \dots \quad \vec{v}_n], \quad (2.5)$$

where each column \vec{v}_i is the eigenvector of the matrix of pair-wise comparisons of alternatives on criterion i . Finally, the ranking of the alternatives is found by

$$\vec{R} = S\vec{v}_A^T, \quad (2.6)$$

where the best alternative has the highest corresponding value in the resulting vector \vec{R} .

Elimination and Choice Translate Reality (ELECTRE)

Another decision technique that shows promise in education is *ELECTRE* (Elimination and Choice Translate Reality). Similar to AHP, *ELECTRE* relies on pair-wise comparison. However, in *ELECTRE*, pair-wise comparison of criteria is unnecessary. This leaves only the pair-wise comparison of alternatives on each of the criteria to be performed. This is seen by some researchers as an advantage it holds over AHP, especially in scenarios with few alternatives and many criteria (Giannoulis and Ishizaka 2010; Odu 2019). In *ELECTRE*, alternative A is said to be strongly preferred to alternative B on criterion c if the difference in performance z on said criterion is larger than some predetermined preference threshold p :

$$A_c \mathbf{P} B_c \rightarrow z_c(A) - z_c(B) > p. \quad (2.7)$$

A is weakly preferred to B on criterion c if the difference in performance is in between the preference threshold p and indifference threshold q :

$$A_c \mathbf{Q} B_c \rightarrow q < z_c(A) - z_c(B) \leq p, \quad (2.8)$$

and A is indifferent to B on criterion c if the difference in performance between the two is smaller than the indifference threshold q :

$$A_c | B_c \rightarrow z_c(A) - z_c(B) \leq q. \quad (2.9)$$

Pair-wise comparisons of the alternatives on each of the criteria are used to find the relative performance of the alternatives, which is then used to calculate the concordance index C . The concordance index is a numerical representation of the truthfulness of the assertion “ A outranks B ”. The concordance indices of each pair of alternatives are then used to distil a ranking of all alternatives. For a complete explanation of the method, refer to Roy 1991.

One of the main issues with these decision-making techniques is that they require the decision-maker to assign some value to the alternatives on each of the criteria. As described in section 2.1.1, the decision maker does not have all the information that is required to precisely assign such scores. One way to overcome this issue is to involve multiple people in the evaluation process (Odu 2019). However, it is often unfeasible for the decision-maker to invite others with the required knowledge to assist in the decision-making process. In the scenario of study programme selection, using a profile of current students to evaluate a study programme on selected criteria may pose a solution to this problem.

2.1.3 Student retention and motivation

The reasons a student has to stay enrolled in a study programme may differ from the reasons they had when they first enrolled. Kori et al. 2016 found that the most important reasons to enrol in a computer science program were *expectations of a good salary* and *good prospects in the labour market*. After the first semester had ended, however, the relative importance of the expected salary had decreased, while the importance of *prior contact with IT* and *intrinsic motivation* (i.e. the idea that IT offers opportunities for self-actualization or the opportunity to be a part of something “big”) had increased. Since the factors influencing study programme selection shift after enrolment is completed and studies have started, preventing dropouts is likely to involve giving prospective students more information on what it is like to have started the program.

2.2 Related work

The studies discussed in this section provide necessary information to be able to design a decision support system for study programme selection. While a lot of research on DSS is done in the field of education, most studies focus on applications in government and healthcare. The main aim of this literature study is to determine which decision-making methods show promise in study programme selection, what benefits a DSS may have when applied to this problem, and what pitfalls to avoid. Each work discussed in this section falls into one or more of the following categories:

- Studies on the applicability of DSS in education management,
- Studies on the applicability of DSS in study programme or educational institution selection,
- Studies on the feasibility of implementation of decision-making methods,
- Studies on the effectiveness of DSS or decision-making methods,
- Literature studies on common benefits and pitfalls of decision-making methods,
- Methods to predict students’ future academic performance.

2.2.1 Decision support systems in education

Designing systems to provide decision support in the field of education is no new endeavour. Eom and Kim 2006 found that 16.07% of scientific articles on DSS between 1995 and 2001 applied their system in education. In this section, several applications of DSS in the field of education are discussed.

ELECTRE

Yanie et al. 2018 found that it is feasible to apply ELECTRE in a web application. However, their study lacks quantitative data on the usability of such systems and the desirability of the outcome of such systems, as they aimed to demonstrate the feasibility of implementation.

When implementing ELECTRE in an application targeted towards a group with little experience regarding such systems, Giannoulis and Ishizaka 2010 found that implementing a full version and a simplified version of the technique is a viable option. The implementation tested in their study was used by students to create a *personalized ranking of British universities*. Participants perceived the possibility to create a ranking based on the criteria they found important as helpful. Furthermore, participants were found to require little explanation to be able to use and understand the system.

AHP

Z. Milojevic and Ž. Milojevic 2015 found that AHP increases confidence in the decision and is perceived as time-saving when implemented in a DSS for minor program selection. Furthermore, they found that presenting AHP in a web-based application was a suitable method to allow students to use the system. Over a third of their participants had high school as their highest completed previous education. Examples of criteria used in the selection process are location, tuition fee, university rank, admission semester, modules offered, campus, language, website quality, and scholarship opportunities.

AHP is argued to be applicable in scenarios where not all criteria for the decision are quantifiable (Badri and Abdulla 2004). Study programme selection is such a scenario; interests, job prospects, prior contact with the field, and the idea that a program provides opportunities for self-actualization are all important factors in study programme selection (El Nemar, Vrontis, and Thrassou 2020; Kori et al. 2016), and are all difficult to quantify.

WSM

Ibrahim and Surya 2019 and Aminudin et al. 2018 used WSM as the decision method for a DSS meant to assist in school selection. Both studies argue that WSM is applicable in this scenario, and Ibrahim and Surya 2019 concludes the system simplifies the decision-making process. Aminudin et al. 2018 recommends combining WSM with some other decision technique as a subject for further research.

One study performed by Daniati and Nugroho 2016 combined WSM with K-means clustering to assist in thesis topic selection. K-means clustering was used to cluster students based on their average grades. These clusters were used to determine the weights of the criteria for each topic. Students using the system would enter their grades for each of the courses, and the system would present them with a ranking of thesis topics suitable for their academic performance. The main aim of this paper was to prove the feasibility of implementation; no data on the desirability of the outcome was presented.

2.2.2 Decision support systems in other fields

Healthcare is one of the most common applications of DSS (Eom and Kim 2006). According to Sutton et al. 2020, clinical decision support systems (CDSS) are most commonly used to increase patient safety by preventing prescription and dosage errors made by physicians. Some pitfalls of CDSS that are likely to be applicable to study programme selection include:

1. Fragmentation of the workflow,
2. Dependency on computer literacy,
3. Impact of poor data quality.

MDSS, or marketing decision support systems, have been found to improve decision-maker performance and decision quality. Furthermore, the effectiveness of such systems is found to be affected by time pressure; as time pressure increases, the positive effects of MDSS use diminish. Finally, the user's cognitive style influences the MDSS's effectiveness as well. High-analytical decision-makers have been found to profit more from the effects of MDSS than low-analytical decision-makers (Van Bruggen, Smidts, and Wierenga 1998).

2.2.3 Predicting academic performance through machine learning

Not all decision support systems rely on decision-making techniques to assist in a decision; in recent decades, machine learning has become an increasingly popular class of methods to assist in multi-criteria decision problems (Eom and Kim 2006). Many classification algorithms have been previously applied to predicting academic performance, a few of which stand out as being both precise and relatively consistent on varying data sets: Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees, and Random Forests (Dierks, Höffler, and Parchmann 2014; Hamim, Benabbou, and Sael

2021; Rastrollo-Guerrero, Gómez-Pulido, and Durán-Domínguez 2020). These methods will be discussed in the following paragraphs.

Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machines (*SVM*) classify data by defining a hyperplane that splits the data into the desired categories. If the data is not linearly separable, the data will be restructured by mapping the scalar dot product of the data points to a high enough dimension that linear separation does become possible. The standard SVM is designed for binary classification, and multi-class classification is done by decomposing the problem into several binary classification problems (Franc and Hlaváč 2002). SVM has been used to classify students' academic performance into "high", "average", and "low", based on psychological parameters including personality and motivation, with an accuracy of around 90% (Chui et al. 2020). When predicting students' academic performance, SVM has been found to outperform most other considered classification algorithms (Rastrollo-Guerrero, Gómez-Pulido, and Durán-Domínguez 2020), although other studies have found that they perform equally to, and are in some cases outperformed by, decision trees and random forests (Alban and Mauricio 2019; Hamim, Benabbou, and Sael 2021; Santos et al. 2019).

Decision Tree

Decision Trees create a *tree* of rules based on the characteristics of the available data, which can thereafter be used to classify new data points. Decision trees have been found to perform slightly more consistently than SVM (Santos et al. 2019), and the accuracy with which they predict academic performance varies from 79% to 89% (Alban and Mauricio 2019).

Random Forest

Random Forests is a predictor consisting of a collection of randomized decision trees. Each of these decision trees is built from a subset of the training data. The final classification is done by a majority vote among the decision trees. Although Santos et al. 2019 state that random forests outperform SVM in most cases, Alban and Mauricio 2019 found that most literature concludes that SVM provide higher accuracy.

2.2.4 Gap analysis

Although many studies apply DSS in the field of education, most tend to focus on the management of educational institutions and governmental decisions concerning education (Ibrahim and Surya 2019; Puspitasari, Wijaya, and Mentari 2020; Zer, Windarto, Wanto, et al. 2019). Although these education management studies provide some valuable insights into the applications of DSS, they tend not to focus on the decisions students have to make. Thus, the results of these studies need to be supplemented with results regarding the way students would interact with DSS.

Several studies attempt to provide these results. Unfortunately, most studies on decision support for study programme selection tend to be mostly implementation-focused. These implementation focused studies aim mainly to prove that implementation is feasible, and *leave the design of the systems largely unverified*. Although the results often show that the system can provide some outcome, gathering feedback on the system's usability and investigating the desirability of the outcome is often outside the scope of these studies.

Another gap that is often present in research on DSS for the study programme dilemma, is that *the criteria used often do not represent the criteria students have* when selecting a study programme. Some common criteria are tuition costs, website quality, the institution's location, and the program's language. Although these criteria may influence the decision, some criteria are more important in study programme selection, such as an interest in the field, career prospects, and the perceived social impact of the field. Furthermore, the less representative criteria may not be applicable in all educational systems. In the Dutch educational system, for example, the tuition fee is not likely to influence most students' decisions since the cost of tuition is the same for most study programmes in most universities.

Most implementations of DSS *require the user to enter the information on each alternative themselves*. This is problematic in the case of study programme selection, since prospective students are missing large parts of the information necessary to make the best decision. Machine learning-based methods could fill this gap, however, the large amounts of data needed to train a machine learning algorithm are not always available. A possible solution to this problem is to incorporate current students' experiences into a DSS. Although Odu 2019 proposed having an evaluation of alternatives performed by many people to determine the performance on each of the criteria, none of the studies reviewed in this chapter used this technique in their research.

Finally, *many experimental studies of DSS verify only one system*. Although doing so does grant insights into the performance of the system in question, it does not answer questions on the system's performance relative to other techniques. Comparing several decision-making techniques could help us understand which techniques perform better than others in certain scenarios.

2.3 Hypotheses

Students who are deciding on a study programme have many alternatives to choose from. This, in combination with the lack of experience needed to properly evaluate the alternatives, will probably cause the student to *satisfice to some degree*. Students are expected to stop looking for new programs after a sufficient number of programs that satisfy their minimal requirements is found. Students may not be fully aware of the criteria they use in their decision, and some students may base their decision on emotion or intuition. Important factors in the students' decision will probably be an interest in the field, future career opportunities, and the perceived social impact of the field. When a student is having difficulty choosing between several study programmes, they may opt for a more systematic strategy, possibly involving comparisons (e.g. a "pros and cons" list) or a ranking. Outside influences are likely to include the opinions of parents, friends, and teachers, and prior academic performance in related subjects.

The profile of current students will probably show some important distinguishing characteristics for each study programme, although some overlap is expected. Students at all three programs will likely show interest in technology and programming to some degree. Students at B.Sc. Informatica are probably more interested in the inner workings of computer systems, software engineering, and to some degree mathematics, while students at B.Sc. Informatiekunde are probably more interested in the impact information technology can have on business and the way humans interact with said technology. Students at B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie are expected to exhibit an interest in psychology, language, and to some degree philosophy.

A decision tree is expected to have a very consistent performance when used as a decision-making method. It is easy to use, since interactions with this system consist of answering several multiple-choice questions, and its deterministic structure leads to consistent results. However, it might be regarded as *too rigid*, which may be detrimental to the confidence users have in its outcome.

An AHP-based method, which allows the user can nuance their answers, might pose a solution to this problem. However, students are likely to have insufficient information on the study programmes to be able to perform pair-wise comparisons of alternatives. This issue might be solved by modifying AHP to use current students' experiences to evaluate the scores on each criterion, leaving only the comparisons of criteria to be performed by the user. A potential drawback of this method is that it requires sufficient data to evaluate the performance of each alternative on each criterion. Furthermore, the user might perform the comparisons inconsistently, for example:

- evaluating *A* to be more important than *B*,
- evaluating *B* to be more important than *C*, but also
- evaluating *C* to be more important than *A*.

This would require the user to *disregard the consistency of their comparisons or re-evaluate their responses*, which might be detrimental to the effectiveness of the decision support.

Finally, a *conversational system* using recent developments in *artificial intelligence and natural language processing* might be able to perform personalized decision support, which could be important when working with individuals with varying decision processes. Furthermore, such a system may not only be able to advise students on which study programmes to consider, but may also be used to answer any questions the student may have. One issue with this technique is that its output is non-deterministic and may in some cases be unpredictable. This could result in inconsistent advice or confusing responses.

2.4 Proposed Method

To confirm whether the expectations discussed in the previous section are correct, *three steps* are needed. The first step, problem analysis, will yield a model of the study programme selection process and three profiles, one for each study programme. The result of the first step will be a set of requirements for a decision support system for study programme selection at CoI. These requirements will be used in the second step, during which a decision support system will be designed. Finally, in the third step, the system's design will be verified and compared to two other decision support methods. Figure 2.1 contains a flow diagram of these steps, each of which will be discussed in the rest of this section.

First, the *gaps in the information* available to high school students and the *problems in their study programme selection process* should be made clear, as this will provide the requirements of the decision support. The information necessary to understand these requirements will be gathered through questionnaires. The first questionnaire was sent to all students who are currently enrolled in one of the programs of CoI and consists mainly of questions about their reasons for enrolment and their experiences with the study programme. The second questionnaire contained mainly questions on the criteria high school students have when selecting a study programme. This questionnaire was sent to several high schools spread evenly throughout Amsterdam and to newly enrolled students at B.Sc. Informatica. For a more in-depth discussion of the questionnaires, refer to sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2. If necessary, the questionnaires will be supplemented by interviews. The responses will be used to create a model of the study programme selection process and will be combined with information from the course catalogue to create a profile of students at CoI. The model and these profiles will be used to determine the requirements of the system.

The second step of this project consists of *designing a DSS for study programme selection*. The system's design will be based on the model of the decision-making process, and the decision support itself will be based on the profiles of students at CoI. The decision-making method used by the system will be a modified version of AHP, called *Profile Aware Pair-wise Additive Weighting* (PAW-PAW). The design of this method is based on the outcome of the questionnaires and the interviews, and will be discussed in further detail in section 4.1.

Finally, *the design of the system will be verified*. To this end, a prototype will be implemented. This prototype will be verified by participants, who will test PAW-PAW, the decision tree and the GPT-based conversational system. Each system's performance will be evaluated via a questionnaire. The results of this questionnaire will be used to deduce an answer to this thesis' main research question.

2.5 Ethical considerations

Some participants who respond to the questionnaire on their considerations for study programme selection, their interests, and their expectations may give information on thoughts and processes that are very personal to them. This information is sensitive and should be treated as such. Thus, any personal information including names and email addresses will be disregarded when analysing the responses, and when citing answers in this thesis, any possible identifying information will be left out. Respondents have been informed through a disclaimer that states that all data used to analyse the results will be anonymous and that personal data will not be analysed. Furthermore, the ethical committee of the University of Amsterdam has been contacted to verify that using the questionnaires would not be problematic.

Figure 2.1: A flow diagram of the methods used to find an answer to the research questions discussed in section 1.2.

The decision support tool should be tested by newly enrolled students and high school students. It is quite likely that some members of this target group are still in the process of selecting a study programme, or to still be evaluating whether they made the right decision. Using the prototype may influence their decision, which could have a large impact on their lives. This could be problematic since the extent to which the tool can provide successful decision support is unknown by the time the first participants will test the tool, and evaluating the outcome of a decision made using said tool is outside the scope of this project. As such, the testers should be made aware that the tool is still in development, and that the outcome should be taken with a grain of salt.

The conversational part of the prototype will make use of a third-party API. Since it is not certain in which ways the information sent to this API will be processed, the involvement of this party should be communicated to the user. Furthermore, the user should be made aware that only the messages they write in the conversational system will be sent to this API. If a tester does not agree with the involvement of a third party, they should be allowed to provide feedback on the other decision-making methods while leaving the answers to the questions concerning the conversational system empty.

Decision Support System Requirement Analysis

In this chapter, the requirements for the decision support system will be analysed. This analysis will be done in several steps. First, two questionnaires will be designed. The first questionnaire aims to shed light on the reasons current students had to enrol in their programs. Furthermore, it is used to find out how students' experiences matched the expectations they had. The other questionnaire is meant to gather information on high school students' study programme selection process. After the questionnaires are analysed, any missing information will be supplemented by performing interviews with first-year students and newly enrolled students. The results of the questionnaires and interviews will be used to create *three profiles*, one for each of the study programmes at CoI, and a *model of the study programme selection process*. Finally, the model and the profiles will be used to determine the requirements for effective decision support. In chapter 4, these requirements will be used to design a decision support system.

3.1 Questionnaire design

3.1.1 Questionnaire on current students' experiences

As mentioned previously, the first questionnaire aims to gather the information needed to create a profile of current students at the College of Informatics. To create such a profile, the following questions should be answered:

- What reasons did students have to enrol in their current study programmes?
- What are the experiences of current students in their study programmes?
- What are the most important interests of students at CoI?
- How do the expectations current students had prior to enrolling match their experiences?

The questionnaire consisted of four sections, with a total of 22 questions. It was sent out to all currently enrolled students at B.Sc. Informatica, B.Sc. Informatiekunde, and B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie at the University of Amsterdam. Since the questionnaire was written in Dutch, the questions discussed in this section will be translated from Dutch to English. Participation in the research was fully anonymous. For the full questionnaire, refer to appendix A.

To ensure the responses match current students' experiences as closely as possible, most questions are open questions. Using mostly multiple choice or Likert scale questions would likely result in incomplete results since they would be based on an incomplete understanding of the study programmes; as mentioned in section 1.2, one of the assumptions in this project is that the available information about the study programmes contains gaps.

Several questions aim to determine what reasons students have to enrol in their study programme, and what subjects interest them most. An example: “Why did you enrol in your current study programme,” “What keywords would you use to describe your current study programme,” and “What keywords would you use to describe your interests?” All answers were provided by the students in free text. To analyse the results of the questionnaire, the responses were labelled. These labels and their frequency can be used to create key-value-based profiles of current students.

Several other questions aim to find out how each study programme matched the students’ expectations. In these questions, students were asked to rate how well their program matched their expectations on a five-point Likert scale. They were asked to follow up with an explanation about the reason they gave a certain rating. The responses to these questions are used to find out how expectations, which are presumably created through the information available before enrolment, match the reality of studying at CoI.

3.1.2 Questionnaire on the study programme selection process

To help understand the decision-making process for study programme selection, a second questionnaire was created (appendix B). This questionnaire aims to answer the following questions:

- What criteria do high school students use when selecting a study programme?
- How do students evaluate the study programmes based on these criteria?
- How do students make their final decision once they are ready to do so?

The questionnaire contained 27 questions, most of which were five-point Likert scales, and was sent out to students at several high schools in Amsterdam. The high schools were selected in such a way that they were evenly spread across Amsterdam and contained both public and special education¹. Furthermore, all schools selected offer VWO-level education, to ensure that the students to whom the questionnaire is sent are able to enrol in a University.

To determine what criteria are important to high school students when selecting a study programme, several questions were asked. Most of these questions asked students to rate how applicable a statement is to them on a five-point Likert scale. Examples of these statements are “The type of job you can get with a certain degree is important in my decision” and “My parents’ opinions do not influence my decision.”

The other two questions are more difficult to answer using a questionnaire. Students were asked how they evaluate study programmes by rating the following statements on a five-point Likert scale: “I have a systematic way to evaluate study programmes” and “My study programme selection is based mostly on intuition or emotion.” Although these questions do grant some insight, they should likely be supplemented with interviews before enough information is found to be able to create a model.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Current students’ experiences

The first questionnaire was responded to by 62 current students at CoI. Of the respondents, 29 were enrolled in B.Sc. Informatica, 10 were enrolled in B.Sc. Informatiekunde, 22 were enrolled in B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie and 1 was enrolled in both B.Sc. Informatica and B.Sc. Wiskunde². Refer to figure 3.1 for a graph of the participants’ study programmes³.

¹Here, *special education* refers to *bijzonder onderwijs*. This term is used for educational institutions that base their education on certain beliefs, such as religious schools and schools based on a specific pedagogical vision. This is not to be confused with *speciaal onderwijs*, which is a term used for educational institutions meant for students that require specific assistance, such as schools for the mentally challenged or schools for the blind.

²Mathematics

³The files containing the raw results are stored following the data management plan of the University of Amsterdam.

Figure 3.1: The study programmes of the respondents to the questionnaire for profiling current students at CoI.

Current students' experiences

Figure 3.2 shows keywords students commonly use to describe their study programmes. The keywords in this figure are the labels that coded the responses students gave to the following questions:

- If you had to describe your study programme, which keywords would you use?
- What is the most important subject in your study programme?

In these questions, no keywords were suggested to the participants. For all keywords shown in figure 3.2, the average difference in percentage of students that mention them for each study programme is 10 percentage points or higher:

$$\frac{|pct_{in} - pct_{ki}| + |pct_{in} - pct_{ik}| + |pct_{ik} - pct_{ki}|}{3} \geq 10\%, \quad (3.1)$$

where pct_{in} is the percentage of students at B.Sc. Informatica that mention a specific keyword, pct_{ki} is the percentage of students at B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie that mention a specific keyword and pct_{ik} is the percentage of students at B.Sc. Informatiekunde that mention a specific keyword. Because the average difference in these percentages is larger than 10, these keywords could be used to differentiate between the three study programmes. Most of these keywords describe subjects in the study programmes. One notable exception is that the word “challenging” is used significantly more often to describe B.Sc. Informatica than the other study programmes.

Current students' reasons to enroll

Other important keywords are the ones used by students when asked to describe their reasons to enrol in their current study programme. These keywords provide insights into the expectations prospective students may have of each of the study programmes. Furthermore, they show what types of considerations prospective students have when selecting a study programme. Keywords in this category are shown in figure 3.3 for B.Sc. Informatica, figure 3.4 for B.Sc. Informatiekunde and figure 3.5 for B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie. The words in these graphs were found by labelling the responses to the following questions:

Figure 3.2: The percentage of respondents that mention important keywords for each study programme. These keywords are determined by the labels that were assigned to responses to the questions “If you had to describe your study programme in keywords, which words would you use?” and “What is the most important subject in your study programme?”. Only the keywords where the average difference in the percentage of respondents that mention them between the study programmes is larger than 10 percentage points (see equation 3.1).

Figure 3.3: The top graph shows the percentage of responses from students at B.Sc. Informatica that mention each reason to enrol in the program. The bottom graph shows the percentage of responses from students at B.Sc. Informatica that mention each specific subject as a reason to enrol. Both interest in a specific subject and a more general interest in the field are considered important when enrolling in the study programme, with career prospects and the broadness of the field being the next most important reasons. Programming and mathematics are the most commonly mentioned subjects that were important for enrolment.

- Why did you enrol in your current study programme?
- Why did you not enrol in one of the other study programmes at the College of Informatics?

For all three programs, an interest in a specific subject was the most common reason to enrol. For B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie and B.Sc. Informatica, a more general interest in the field, career prospects, and the broadness of the field were other notable reasons. For both B.Sc. Informatiekunde and B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie, not satisfying the terms of admission for B.Sc. Informatica was a relatively common reason. For both B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie and B.Sc. Informatica, programming and mathematics are mentioned as important reasons to enrol. Paradoxically, not liking mathematics is an important reason to enrol in B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie as well. This can be explained by some students choosing B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie over B.Sc. Informatiekunde because they like mathematics, and others choosing B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie over B.Sc. Informatica because they dislike mathematics. For B.Sc. Informatiekunde, specific subjects commonly mentioned are an interest in humans and technology, and disliking mathematics.

How well the study programmes match students' expectations

Although the keywords mentioned in the previous paragraph provide useful information about students' motivations before enrolling, they are not guaranteed to accurately describe what stu-

Figure 3.4: The top graph shows the percentage of responses from students at B.Sc. Informatiekunde that mention each reason to enrol in the program. The bottom graph shows the percentage of responses from students at B.Sc. Informatiekunde that mention each specific subject as a reason to enrol. An interest in a specific subject is the reason that is mentioned most, not satisfying the terms of admission for B.Sc. Informatica comes second, and career prospects and prior experiences with the field share third place. All other reasons are mentioned by only one student. Notable is that *human* and *technology* are the subjects that are mentioned most often, with not being interested in mathematics being a close third.

Figure 3.5: The top graph shows the percentage of responses from students at B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie that mention each reason to enrol in the program. The bottom graph shows the percentage of responses from students at B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie that mention each specific subject as a reason to enrol. The most common reasons to enrol in the program are an interest in a specific subject and a more general interest in the field. The specific subjects mentioned most often are *programming*, *mathematics*, *not mathematics*, *psychology*, and *technical depth*. Notable is that both *mathematics* and *not mathematics* are mentioned equally often; this could be explained by some students choosing B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie over B.Sc. Informatiekunde because they liked mathematics, and other students choosing B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie over B.Sc. Informatica because they disliked mathematics.

Figure 3.6: Students' responses when asked how well their study programme matched their expectations. The answers were given on a five-point Likert scale. The rating is plotted against the percentage of students in the respective study programme that gave this rating. The average rating is 3.9 for B.Sc. Informatica, 3.6 for B.Sc. Informatiekunde, and 3.8 for B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie.

dents' experiences at each study programme turned out to be. To determine which of these expectations proved realistic, students were asked to rate how well their study programme matched their expectations on a five-point Likert scale and to explain why they gave that rating. Figure 3.6 shows that the programs match most students' expectations relatively well, although a large minority of students give a relatively low rating (3 out of 5). B.Sc. Informatiekunde is rated lowest with an average of 3.6 out of 5, and B.Sc. Informatica is rated highest with a 3.9 out of 5. B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie sits in the middle, with students giving it a 3.8 out of 5 on average. The double bachelor Wiskunde and Informatica scores a 4 out of 5 on average, however, only one student of this program responded to the questionnaire. When asked what information they would have needed to improve this score, 28% of the students who answered the question responded that they would have liked a more realistic description of the study programme. Several of those students stated that information on the experiences of current students would have been valuable to them. The reasons students gave for their rating will be discussed in the rest of this section.

Figure 3.7 shows the responses students of B.Sc. Informatica gave when asked to explain why the study programme did or did not match their expectations. Notable is that the most common response was that the workload was higher than expected. This seems to correspond to the number of students that mention *challenging* as a keyword to describe B.Sc. Informatica (figure 3.2). Similarly, the high prevalence of the keyword *mathematics* in figure 3.2 is accompanied by students mentioning that the program included more mathematics than they expected. Figure 3.8 shows in which ways B.Sc. Informatiekunde matched the expectations that students had of it before enrolling. Most notable is that the program turned out to be less human-focused than expected for 20% of the respondents. Although some students expected the program to be more human-focused, figure 3.2 shows the program to be the most human-focused out of the three study programmes discussed in this thesis. The responses of students at B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie can be found in figure 3.9. The most common responses are that the study programme is more theoretical than expected and that the workload is lower than expected. To some students, the program turned out to be more research-oriented than expected.

Figure 3.7: Responses from students at B.Sc. Informatica when asked to explain why their study programme did or did not meet their expectations. The most common response was that had a higher workload than they expected. Other notable responses are that the program is as programming-focused as expected, and that the program includes more mathematics and is more theoretical than expected.

Figure 3.8: Responses from students at B.Sc. Informatiekunde when asked to explain why their study programme did or did not meet their expectations. Most notable is that the program is less human-focused than expected.

Figure 3.9: Responses from students at B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie when asked to explain why their study programme did or did not meet their expectations. The most common responses were that the program was more theoretical than expected and that the workload was lower than expected.

3.2.2 Course Catalogues

The method used to analyse the course catalogues is similar to the method used to analyse the responses to the questionnaires. Each course in the study programmes was labelled using the goals, description, and required knowledge from the course catalogue. A course could be assigned one or more labels. The labels describe both the main subject of the course and the skills necessary to complete it. For example, *Numerical Recipes Project*, a course in the third semester of B.Sc. Informatica, is a course in which students are taught calculus, and how to use Python to apply concepts of numerical mathematics in a research project. As such, it was assigned the labels *wiskunde* (mathematics), *programmeren* (programming), *academische vaardigheden* (academic skills) and *project* (*Informatica - Studiegids 2022 - 2023 2022; Informatiekunde - Studiegids 2022 - 2023 2022; Informatiekunde - Studiegids 2022 - 2023 2022*).

The labels were weighted by the amount of ECTS credits that can be achieved in the associated course. The results are shown in figure 3.10. Notable is that both programming (*programmeren*) and academic skills (*academische vaardigheden*) are important subjects in all three study programmes. B.Sc. Informatica appears to focus more on mathematics, theoretical aspects of the field, and software design than the other two study programmes. As expected, machine learning, psychology (*psychologie*), language (*taal*), and to a lesser degree philosophy (*filosofie*) are important subjects for B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie. In B.Sc. Informatiekunde, data science (*data*), human (*mens*), and organization science (*organisatiekunde*) are the most common subjects.

It is noteworthy that the *course catalogues show some similarities to current students' experiences*. Some examples of notable similarities are:

- Programming is common in all three study programmes,
- Mathematics and theory are more common in B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie and B.Sc. Informatica than in B.Sc. Informatiekunde,
- B.Sc. Informatiekunde has a larger focus on multidisciplinary than the other programs,
- Data science (labelled *data*) is more important in B.Sc. Informatiekunde than in the other study programmes.

To incorporate both current students' experiences and the study programme's intentions into the profile of a student at each program, the results from the questionnaire are combined with the results from the course catalogues. This was done by averaging the percentage associated with each keyword. Figure 3.11 shows the result.

Figure 3.10: The percentage of ECTS credits that involve a certain subject for each study programme. The keywords were found by labelling each course based on the information in the respective course catalogues. Since the study programmes and the target audience of the system have Dutch as their main language, the keywords were not translated into English.

Figure 3.11: The relative importance of several distinguishing characteristics of each of the study programmes. The values were found by averaging the percentage of respondents that mention each keyword when describing their study programme and the percentage of ECTS in each program that involve certain subjects.

3.2.3 The study programme selection process

Interviews

To supplement the information from the questionnaire, seven interviews were conducted. Six of these interviews were conducted with newly enrolled students at B.Sc. Informatica. One interview was conducted with a first-year student at B.Sc. Informatiekunde. Students were asked questions about their study programme selection process, what criteria they used when making their decision, how they found the information they needed to make their decision, and whether they had used any decision support systems to aid them in making their decision. The responses of the interviewees are discussed below.

When asked what criteria they used when selecting a study programme, *most interviewees' responses matched current students' reasons to enrol*. Five out of seven had taken career prospects into account during the selection process. One student gave prior experiences with the field as the sole reason to enrol in B.Sc. Informatica. Six out of the seven interviewees mentioned an interest in a specific subject. Two of the new Informatica students mentioned a more general interest in mathematics, one mentioned not being interested in statistics and being interested in programming, and one student was specifically interested in working with the *C* programming language. The student at B.Sc. Informatiekunde had switched from B.Sc. Gezondheid en Leven because she wanted to study more technology-related subjects. One student stated that her parents' opinion had influenced her decision to enrol in Informatica instead of Psychology. Interestingly, one student mentioned he decided not to enrol in B.Sc. Informatiekunde because he thought the program would focus too much on statistical mathematics. Since B.Sc. Informatiekunde does not have any courses on statistical mathematics, this indicates that the content of the program was unclear to him.

All students described an *orientation phase* in which they gathered information on which study programmes are available to them and what criteria they have for a study programme. Some students generated an extensive list of programs to take into consideration during this phase, while others stopped searching for information earlier. Three students' descriptions of this part of the process showed clear signs of satisficing; these students stopped looking for new study programmes after they had found three or fewer study programmes that fit their criteria.

The ways students decided on a study programme varied. Although most students stated their decision was mostly based on *emotion or intuition*, one student described a more *systematic approach*. This student had generated an extensive list of study programmes that were available to them and evaluated them one by one based on the information on the universities' websites. After this evaluation, he was left with seven study programmes. Although his approach had been systematic up until that point, the student made the final decision between these seven programs based on intuition.

Gathering information was done mostly via the internet. Students often mention the study programme's website as an important source. A few students got their information through acquaintances who are enrolled in a study programme they were interested in. Two students had not found the course catalogue, and as such were missing information on what to expect from the study programme's courses. Both of these students stated they would have wanted to be able to use the information from the course catalogue when making their decision.

Two of the interviewed students used a decision support system during their selection process. One of these students had used two decision support systems; one consisted of a list of Likert scale questions and one consisted of a set of "yes or no" questions presented like the popular dating app Tinder⁴. She said the Tinder-like system was more user-friendly, but the outcome of the Likert scale questions seemed more reliable. The main reason for this was that the Tinder-like presentation of criteria did not encourage her to think critically about her answer, while the Likert scales did. A problem with the Likert scale-based system was that all questions were shown simultaneously, which was perceived by the student as overwhelming. Both systems discussed by the student resulted in a ranking of study programmes. She did not use these rankings to make her final decision, although she did use them as sources of information during the previously described orientation phase. The other student who used a decision support system used a

⁴In this system, the user was presented with an image that represented a criterion, and uses a "Like" or "Dislike" button to work towards a result

system that presented the user with a set of pair-wise comparisons. He had disregarded the result of this system because it only allowed him to select which criterion was more important. He thinks he might not have dismissed the outcome if the system allowed more nuance by, for example, providing “the criteria are equally important” as an option. When asked, he confirmed that allowing the user to rate the relative importance of the criteria would have increased his confidence in the system. Both students indicated that they would prefer a system that does not require them to download a program or create an account, as opposed to a system that does.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire on the study programme selection process received twenty responses, all from newly enrolled students at B.Sc. Informatica. The most popular sources of information were the University’s website (70% of respondents), the open days (60% of respondents), and Studiekeuze123 (35% of respondents). Since current students indicated that they would have liked a more realistic idea of what the study programme entails (section 3.2.1), the course catalogue is a valuable source of information for prospective students. However, *only three students (15%) had used the information from the course catalogue when making their decision*⁵.

3.3 Modelling the study programme selection process

The results discussed in section 3.2.1 can be used to determine what factors influence the decision-making process when selecting a study programme. The prevalence of *specific subject* as a reason to enrol shows that the process is partially rational, with students using information available to form an idea of what each program is about, and using these ideas to choose a program that matches their interests. *Career prospects* being in the top four of each of these study programmes is in line with the findings of the study discussed in section 2.1.3. Furthermore, *shortage of information* being mentioned by several students of B.Sc. Informatica shows that students are unable to accurately consider the outcome of each of the alternatives, combined with *satisficing* being described by several students in both the questionnaires⁶ and the interviews, indicates that the bounded rationality model is applicable in this scenario.

The results from the interviews indicate that some students may adopt a systematic approach, while others base their decision mostly on intuition. In both cases, students gather information throughout the process; the difference lies in the way this information is processed. Students will orient themselves on the different study programmes available to them, but will stop this orientation once a satisfactory number of options have been found. Some students will enrol in the first study programme that fits their criteria, while others keep gathering information until they have found a set of study programmes from which to select the one that best matches their interests. Some students keep their options open, enrolling in several study programmes and postponing the decision until the start of the academic year.

Prospective students’ decision-making process consists of four phases: *orientation*, *evaluation*, *decision*, and *retrospection*. In the orientation phase, the students orient themselves on what study programmes are available to them and what it is they are looking for in a study programme. In the evaluation phase, which may start before orientation has ended, the student gathers information on how each study programme found during orientation matches their criteria. If a program does not match the student’s criteria, it will no longer be considered a viable alternative. Some students may have a systematic approach to this phase, while others base the outcome of the evaluation phase solely on intuition. If satisficing occurs during the evaluation phase, both the orientation phase and the evaluation phase will end. When a student feels like they are ready to make their decision, the evaluation phase ends and the student moves into the decision phase. At what point a student is ready to decide varies per individual. In the decision phase, the student has reduced the number of alternatives to a relatively small number and makes the final decision on which study programme they will enrol in. After the student has enrolled and courses

⁵The files containing the raw results are stored following the data management plan of the University of Amsterdam.

⁶The label *satisficing* was given to responses similar to “I liked Informatica, so I didn’t consider the other options.”

Figure 3.12: The model of high school students' study programme selection process. The rectangles show the order in which the orientation phase (1), evaluation phase (2), decision phase (3) and retrospection phase (4) occur. The orientation and evaluation phase may be cut short when satisficing occurs. Information gathering (5) is a continuous process that is present throughout all phases of the decision-making process. The ellipse at the bottom shows the five criteria that are most commonly used by students during study programme selection (6).

have started, the retrospection phase starts. In this phase, the student uses the information that becomes available through experience to re-evaluate their decision. Some students may choose to alter their decision by dropping out or enrolling in a different study programme. Figure 3.12 contains a visualization of this model.

3.4 Profiling current students

In this section, a profile of the typical student at each of the study programmes at CoI is created. These profiles are used to determine how the three decision-making methods match prospective students to the study programmes. Each profile consists of a set of keys, each of which has a value associated with it.

The keywords that distinguish between the study programmes (figure 3.11) and how the study programmes matched or didn't match students' expectations (figures 3.7, 3.8 and 3.9) were used to determine the criteria to be used for decision support. The resulting criteria are:

- The amount of mathematics in the study programme,
- The amount of data science in the study programme,
- The amount of organization science in the study programme,
- The amount of machine learning in the program,
- How human-focused the program is,
- The amount of programming involved in the program,
- How theoretical the program is,
- The amount of psychology in the program,
- The multidisciplinaryity of the program,
- How business-focused the program is.

Note that the keywords *challenging and technology were disregarded* when deriving these criteria. The reason *challenging* was left out, is that students may be turned off of enrolling when they see a programme is considered difficult, even if the programme is a perfect fit for them. Furthermore, what is challenging to one person may not be for someone else. The reason

Table 3.1: The profile of students at B.Sc. Informatica. The keywords and associated values are based on the percentage of students that use certain keywords to describe their study programme and the subjects of the courses in the study programme.

B.Sc. Informatica	
Mathematics	40.6
Data Science	8.3
Organization Science	0.0
Machine Learning	4.3
Human	0.0
Programming	66.8
Theory	27.7
Psychology	0.0
Multidisciplinary	1.7
Business	0.0

Table 3.2: The profile of students at B.Sc. Informatica. The keywords and associated values are based on the percentage of students that use certain keywords to describe their study programme and the subjects of the courses in the study programme.

B.Sc. Informatiekunde	
Mathematics	2.0
Data Science	36.0
Organization Science	30.0
Machine Learning	7.0
Human	26.0
Programming	41.0
Theory	2.0
Psychology	7.0
Multidisciplinary	23.0
Business	20.0

technology is disregarded as a criterion, is that all three study programmes have technology as one of their main focuses; using this criterion may yield confusing results (e.g. students may be led to believe that B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie does not involve any technology at all).

The relative weight of each key was calculated by averaging the percentage of ECTS that involve the subject and the percentage of responses that mention the keyword associated with said subject. These values can be found in figure 3.11. The resulting key-weight pairs can be found in the profiles in tables 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3.

3.5 The requirements

The requirements of the decision support system can be found in the problems students deal with during and after study programme selection. Students expressed a desire for a more realistic view of the study programme during the selection process, but are not always able to find the course catalogue. Most students use specific subjects covered in a study programme as an important criterion for their decision, however, the results of the interviews and questionnaires show that students do not always have an accurate understanding of the study programmes' subjects. Finally, not all students know a current student at one of the programs, and as such, miss information on the ways the program does not match common expectations.

In the interviews, students who had used decision support systems for study programme selection found two main problems with such systems. The first problem is that some of these systems present the user with binary choices. The lack of nuance in the answers the students are able to give in these systems causes them to question the reliability of the outcome. The

Table 3.3: The profile of students at B.Sc. Informatica. The keywords and associated values are based on the percentage of students that use certain keywords to describe their study programme and the subjects of the courses in the study programme.

B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie	
Mathematics	37.7
Data Science	4.2
Organization Science	0.0
Machine Learning	30.5
Human	2.1
Programming	61.7
Theory	8.5
Psychology	22.4
Multidisciplinary	6.8
Business	0.0

second problem is the tradeoff between the usability of the system and the ability of the system to encourage critical thinking by the user; a system that is more fun or easy to use may cause the user to think less deeply about the answers they give, which may be detrimental to the decision support.

A decision support system is most likely used during the orientation and evaluation phases of the study programme selection process. The students that did employ a systematic approach at some point in the selection process did so in these phases. Furthermore, all the interviewed students based their final decision, made during the decision phase, on emotion or intuition. During the orientation phase, students gather a list of available study programmes, and during the evaluation phase, students try to dismiss as many alternatives as possible based on the information available to them. Thus, a decision support system is likely to be of more value to prospective students if it provides information on multiple study programmes as opposed to only one study programme.

Although the differences in the ways that students go through the study programme selection process indicate that it might be impossible to create a “one system fits all” solution to the problem, the results discussed in this section do allow us to determine a set of requirements for effective decision support. A decision support system for study programme selection at CoI should:

- Base its outcome on current students’ experiences and the contents of the course catalogue to provide a realistic image of the study programmes,
- Present the user with questions that require simple answers, so the system is easy to use,
- Provide the option to nuance these answers to promote critical thinking and increase the perceived reliability,
- Provide a list of study programmes as the outcome to enable students to select multiple alternatives to look into further.

Decision support system design

During the study programme selection process, high school students struggle with gaps in the available information and the large number of options. To help students with their decision, the experiences of current students can be used; these experiences often prove a valuable source of information for students who re-evaluate their study programme selection. In this chapter, the requirements discussed in section 3.5 are used to design a decision technique and a decision support system.

4.1 Profile Aware Pair-Wise Additive Weighting

Pair-wise comparison appears to be a suitable way to assist in complex decisions. One of the interviewed students indicated that a decision support system that allows the decision maker to rate the relative importance of the criteria on a scale would be a useful tool in the study programme selection process. Another student indicated that a Likert scale encourages critical thinking. This indicates that AHP could be a viable method to support the study programme selection process. However, students lack the information needed to perform pair-wise comparisons of study programmes, indicating that neither ELECTRE nor AHP is fully applicable in this scenario. For this reason, a new decision-making method is introduced; *Profile Aware Pair-wise Additive Weighting* (PAW-PAW).

PAW-PAW makes use of the elements of AHP that are applicable to the process as described in the previous chapters of this thesis. These elements are (section 2.1.2):

- Weighting the criteria using pair-wise comparisons,
- Using the eigenvalue-method to determine the consistency of these comparisons.

Instead of pair-wise comparisons between alternatives, the previously created profiles will be used to determine each alternative's score on each criterium. The final ranking of alternatives will be calculated by applying the Weighted Sum Method (section 2.1.2), using the values from these profiles and the weights determined by the user.

4.1.1 Example

This section will show an example of how the final ranking of study programmes is derived from pair-wise comparisons. In this example, the decision maker is assumed to base their decision on three criteria:

1. How theoretical the study programme is,
2. The amount of machine learning in the study programme,
3. The amount of organization science in the study programme.

The student will have to perform three comparisons. Say the student rates the relative importance of the criteria as follows:

- Machine learning is more important than theory; score (2, 1) is 5,
- Organization science and theory are equally important; score (1, 3) is 1,
- Machine learning is more important than organization science; score (2, 3) is 6.

This would lead to the following matrix:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1/5 & 1 \\ 5 & 1 & 6 \\ 1 & 1/6 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.1)$$

The largest eigenvalue λ_{max} of matrix A is

$$\lambda_{max} \approx 3.0037, \quad (4.2)$$

which is close to the number of criteria, indicating that the comparisons were performed consistently. The eigenvector that corresponds to this value is

$$v_{\lambda_{max}} \approx \begin{bmatrix} 1.06266 \\ 5.64622 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.3)$$

which, after normalizing it so that its values sum to 1, becomes

$$v_A = \begin{bmatrix} 0.13785 \\ 0.73243 \\ 0.12972 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.4)$$

The values of this vector show, from top to bottom, the respective weights of the three criteria mentioned previously. Using the values from the profiles, and applying the weighted sum method on these values using the weights from v_A , results in the following score for B.Sc. Informatica:

$$S_{inf} = \sum_{i=1}^3 c_i v_A[i] = 27.7 \cdot 0.13785 + 4.3 \cdot 0.73243 + 0.0 \cdot 0.12972 = 6.9, \quad (4.5)$$

where c_i is the score of B.Sc. Informatica on the i th criterion and $v_A[i]$ is the weight of the i th criterion. Finally, performing the same calculations for the other two programs results in the following ranking:

1. B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie (23.5),
2. B.Sc. Informatiekunde (9.2),
3. B.Sc. Informatica (6.9).

4.2 The design of the system

Since the system should be easily accessible, without requiring the user to download or install a program, the system is designed as a *client-server architecture*. The client will manage the interactions between the user and the system. The server will contain the knowledge base, provide the client with the requested information, and perform the calculations to generate the final ranking. The knowledge base holds the relevant information about the study programmes, the criteria, and the scores the study programmes have on each criterion. Figure 4.1 shows a diagram of the architecture.

The user will access the system through their internet browser. First, the user selects which criteria to use, so they can reduce the number of comparisons to be done if desired. The user

Figure 4.1: The system's architecture. The core of the application is the back-end, which uses Django and Django REST framework, both Python libraries. The back-end runs on a Linux server with Apache2. Data is stored in an SQLite database. The front-end is provided by a React JS application, which runs in the client's browser.

Figure 4.2: The use case diagram showing the actors that interact with the system, and what use cases each actor interacts with. A prospective student can use the decision support technique PAW-PAW, a modified version of AHP. The admin can change the values used in PAW-PAW.

will then be presented with a pair-wise comparison between two of the selected criteria. The user first chooses which criterion is more important, or clicks “equally important”. If the user selects one of the criteria, they are presented with a set of radio buttons that allow them to nuance their response by rating the relative importance of the selected criterion. When the comparison is done, the user clicks *next* to be presented with the next pair-wise comparison. After all comparisons are done, the user will be presented with a ranking of the three study programmes and their final scores. To allow the user to fix any mistakes they may have made, they are able to restart the process at any time. Figure 4.2 shows the use-case diagram of these interactions.

The back-end will be created using Django, a Python-based model-view-template framework for web applications. For ease of implementation, data will be stored using Django’s default SQLite database. Communication with the front-end of the application will be done through a RESTful API using Django REST Framework, a Python library that extends Django by implementing several classes that can be used to return JSON in views. The front-end will be created using React, a JavaScript framework that is designed to allow for easy creation of reusable UI components. The user will use this React application to interact with the system’s back-end via a GUI.

Figure 4.3 shows an ER diagram of the database’s structure. The relevant entities are study programmes and criteria. Each study programme is identified with an ID and has a name. Each criterion has a description and a long description and is identified with an ID. The *has score on* relation between the two entities has a value that represents the study programme’s score on a criterion.

The back-end provides the endpoints needed for the front-end to retrieve the data it needs. These endpoints are as follows:

`/criteria/` A GET request to this endpoint is responded to with an array containing all available criteria.

`/pawpaw-result/` A POST request to this endpoint is responded to with an array containing the study programmes’ total scores. A JSON object with the keys `matrix` and `criteria` should be provided, where `matrix` is a 2D array that represents the matrix in equation 2.3, and `criteria` is an array containing the IDs of the used criteria.

Finally, the front-end provides a GUI to allow the user to interact with the system. As is usual in React applications, the front-end consists of several functional components. The first

Figure 4.4: The design of the application’s front-end. **(1)** The landing page of the application. Here, the `PawPaw` component displays a start button. **(2)** The criteria selection stage. Here, the `PawPaw` component displays the `CriteriaSelector` component **(2a)**, which allows the user to select which criteria to use. **(3)** A pair-wise comparison. Here, the main `PawPaw` component shows the `Comparison` component **(3a)**, which is used to select which of the two criteria is more important. Here, an example is shown where the user has selected one of the criteria as the more important criterion, and the `LikertScale` component **(3b)** is displayed. **(4)** The results page. Here, the `PawPaw` component displays the `Result` component **(4b)**, which shows the ranking based on the comparisons performed by the user along with each study programme’s total score.

Demonstration and Validation

Validating the design of PAW-PAW requires several steps. First, the design must be implemented in a prototype. Second, an implementation of the other methods with which PAW-PAW will be compared should be made. Third, the design and implementation of the systems should be verified. Finally, the results of these experiments should be used to formulate an answer to this thesis' main research question.

Verifying the systems' design and implementation is done through experimentation. The experiments should gather feedback on the intended users' experience using the system, and critically evaluate each system's results. To this end, the following experiments will be conducted:

E₁: Participants use the systems and respond to a questionnaire to provide feedback,

E₂: Self-evaluation; testing each system to identify problems that participants might not find.

For each of the three systems, the questionnaire will provide information on:

- *Answer quality*: the user's ability to provide sufficient information to the system,
- *Confidence*: how confident the user is in the system's result,
- *Time saving*: the degree to which the user perceives the system as time-saving,
- *Usability*: how easy it is to use the system.

The self-evaluation experiment will yield at least an understanding of the correctness of each of the systems' results. A diagram of the experiments can be found in figure 5.1.

The experiments are designed to indicate which of the three methods works best when applied in a study programme selection tool. However, it is possible that the results are not as definite as would be necessary to draw such a conclusion. As shown in chapter 3, not all students go through the decision-making process in the same way. Furthermore, in chapter 2 we saw that the effectiveness of a decision support system depends on the user's decision-making style. Because of this, there is likely no "one system fits all" solution to the study programme dilemma. This means that all three methods may show similar results, with all three being preferred by some students, while not doing so well for other students. If this is the case, it implies that combining several methods would pose a better way to provide decision support. If so, an idea on how to combine the methods tested in this thesis will be proposed as a subject for future research.

5.1 Implementation of the design

The system was implemented in two separate applications; a Django REST API as the back-end, and a React app as the front-end¹. The system was deployed on a Linux machine running an Apache2 server, and the front-end was publicly accessible via the web address ckonings.com.

¹The code can be found in this GitHub repository: <https://github.com/CoenKonings/study-program-selection-tool>.

Figure 5.1: A flow diagram showing how the experiments will be performed.

```
Criterion List
API endpoint that allows Criteria to be viewed.

GET /criteria/

HTTP 200 OK
Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS
Content-Type: application/json
Vary: Accept

[
  {
    "id": 1,
    "description": "Mathematics"
  },
  {
    "id": 2,
    "description": "Psychology"
  }
]
```

Figure 5.2: The debug view of the criteria endpoint.

The back-end consists of the models needed to represent the data to be stored in the database. Furthermore, it contains the views needed to implement the endpoints discussed in section 4.2 (figures 5.2 and 5.3). The most important of the endpoints, `/pawpaw-result/`, accepts a POST request containing an array of criteria IDs and a 2D array that represents the comparison matrix. NumPy is used to calculate the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of this matrix, which are then processed using the weighted sum method.

The front-end of the application consists of a main **App** component, which contains the **PawPaw** component. The latter of these components contains the state of the application, including the 2D array in which the results of the pair-wise comparisons will be stored. First, the **PawPaw** component displays the **CriteriaSelector** component (figure 5.4), allowing the user to select which criteria to use. The user is then presented with several pair-wise comparisons using the **Comparison** component (figure 5.5). When all comparisons are done, the **Result** component shows a ranking of study programmes (figure 5.6).

5.2 Experiment setup

5.2.1 Decision tree and conversational system design

The design will be verified by comparing PAW-PAW with a decision tree and a conversational system. To make it as easy as possible for participants to try all three systems, the two methods used for comparison are integrated into the same system as PAW-PAW. When the user selects the decision tree, they are presented with a question. The user clicks the button corresponding to their answer to be presented with the next question until a leaf of the tree presents them with a result. The conversational system asks the user questions about their interests, to which the user can respond by providing information or asking questions of their own. At some point, the conversational system advises the user on which study programme best fits their interests. Figure 5.7 shows a use-case diagram of the system.

The decision tree's design is based on the information from the course catalogue (figure 3.10). Some of its questions were designed to eliminate one of the alternatives. For example, the question "Are you interested in mathematics?" and its follow-up question "Is it important to you that a study programme involves a lot of mathematics?" were designed to possibly eliminate B.Sc. Informatiekunde as an alternative. Other questions were designed to figure out how the user's interests align with each of the study programmes. Once the user has provided enough answers that indicate a specific study programme matches their interests more than the others, they are shown the result. Appendix D shows the design of the decision tree.

Paw Paw Result

API endpoint that allows posting the results of pair-wise comparisons, and returns a ranking of StudyPrograms.

POST /pawpaw-result/

```
HTTP 200 OK
Allow: POST, OPTIONS
Content-Type: application/json
Vary: Accept

{
  "ranking": [
    {
      "study_program": {
        "id": 1,
        "name": "BSc Informatica"
      },
      "score": 10.762751319526348
    },
    {
      "study_program": {
        "id": 2,
        "name": "BSc Informatiekunde"
      },
      "score": 20.283678487424773
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 5.3: The debug view of the result endpoint.

PAW-PAW

Selecteer de criteria die je wil meenemen in je keuze.

Aantal geselecteerde criteria: 4

Aantal vragen dat je moet beantwoorden: 6

- Mathematics
- Psychology
- Programming
- Business
- Theory
- Multidisciplinary

Verder

Terug naar hoofdmenu

Figure 5.4: The criteria selection screen.

PAW-PAW

Selecteer wat je belangrijker vindt:

Mathematics
of
Psychology

Mathematics Even belangrijk Psychology

Hoe veel belangrijker is dit criterium?

1 (iets belangrijker) - 8 (veel belangrijker)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8

Verder Terug naar hoofdmenu

Figure 5.5: The pair-wise comparison screen.

PAW-PAW

Resultaat:

De bovenste studie past het best bij je antwoorden, de onderste het minst goed. De getallen achter de namen van de studies geven de onderlinge verhoudingen aan van hoe hoog ze scoren bij jouw interesses.

1. BSc Kunstmatige Intelligentie (26)
2. BSc Informatica (13)
3. BSc Informatiekunde (9)

Je antwoorden op de vragen waren consistent.

Terug naar hoofdmenu

Figure 5.6: The result screen.

Figure 5.7: A use-case diagram of the system that integrates three decision-making methods: PAW-PAW, a decision tree, and a conversational system.

Figure 5.8: The landing page of the application, which allows the user to select which system to use.

Figure 5.9: A question from the decision tree.

The conversational system is primed using a prompt that describes what it should do (appendix E). In this prompt, the system is instructed to ask the user at least three follow-up questions in separate messages, to keep its messages on the shorter side, and not to provide a result before the eighth message of the conversation. Furthermore, it is provided a summary of the profiles discussed in section 3.4. As the course catalogue and most other information on the study programmes is publicly available, it is assumed that the GPT model is already aware of the subjects common to each of the study programmes. The time it takes the model to respond increases as the amount of text it has to process grows; the prompt aims to balance providing enough information and instructions with the time it takes to generate a response.

5.2.2 Decision tree and conversational system implementation

A `SystemSelector` component was placed between the `App` component and the `PawPaw` component. `SystemSelector` presents the user with a menu that allows them to select which of the methods to use (figure 5.8). At all times, the user can click a button to return to the main menu of this component.

When the user chooses the decision tree, they are presented with a multiple-choice question that is associated with the root of the decision tree. Each of the responses to that question leads to a new node, containing another question (figure 5.9). The user traverses the decision tree until one of the leaves leads them to a result, which is one of the study programmes.

The decision tree makes use of the back-end through the following endpoints: `/decision-trees/` retrieves all decision trees from the database², `/decision-trees/{id}` retrieves a specific decision tree from the database, and `/node/{id}` is used to traverse the decision tree by selecting a

²Although the database is designed to hold multiple decision trees, only one is used in this experiment.

Node Instance

API endpoint that allows Nodes to be viewed.

```
GET /nodes/2/
```

```
HTTP 200 OK
Allow: GET, HEAD, OPTIONS
Content-Type: application/json
Vary: Accept

{
  "id": 2,
  "question": null,
  "result": {
    "id": 1,
    "name": "BSc Informatica"
  }
}
```

Figure 5.10: The debug view of the nodes endpoint, showing an HTTP response containing a leaf of the decision tree. Leaves contain no question, since they lead to a result. The result is one of the study programmes.

Figure 5.11: The GUI of the conversational system showing part of a conversation.

specific node. Each selected node will either lead to other nodes via the node's question and its possible responses or, if the node is a leaf, will lead to a study programme (figure 5.10).

The conversational system, which was implemented using OpenAI's *GPT 3.5 turbo* model, asks the user questions about their interests and allows them to provide information or ask questions. At some point, this system advises the user on which of the study programmes best fits their criteria. The conversation will keep going until the user decides they have gathered enough information, or until the total amount of messages reaches 50. This limit was imposed to limit the cost of the API calls. Figure 5.11 shows the GUI of the system.

The interactions between the front-end and OpenAI's API go through the back-end, which allows posting the conversation history to the `/conversation/` endpoint. This endpoint leads to a view that first verifies the validity of the request data. If the data contains a valid conversation, the system's response will be retrieved using the *openai* Python library.

5.2.3 Questionnaire for design validation

The questionnaire is designed to answer several questions regarding the usability and effectiveness of the three methods. These questions are as follows:

- Is the user able to provide sufficient information about their preferences when using the system?

- Is the user confident that the system’s result is correct?
- Does the user think using the system during study programme selection would save time?
- Is the system easy to use?

The questionnaire consists of four sections. Each of the first three sections consists of nine statements, of which participants rate the applicability on a five-point Likert scale. Two statements provide information on the system’s usability, one statement on its time saving capabilities, three statements on the confidence the user has in the results and three statements provide feedback on the quality of the information the user is able to provide. The final section of the questionnaire consists of one multiple choice questions and four open questions. In the multiple choice question, the user selects which of the three systems they would most likely use when selecting a study programme. Three of the open questions instruct the participant to describe what they would change about each system. The final question allows participants to provide any feedback they might still have. The full questionnaire is included in appendix C.

5.2.4 Self-evaluation

During self-evaluation, several scenarios will be tested on each of the systems. These scenarios are based on the types of criteria a prospective student may have when selecting a study programme, such as career aspirations or specific subjects they are interested in. Furthermore, several levels of certainty regarding these criteria will be used; some prospective students may know what they are looking for better than others.

The scenarios to be tested include some best-case scenarios and several edge-case scenarios. The best case scenario is a user who is aware of their motivations, and whose criteria match one of the study programmes exactly. The edge cases include users whose interests lie somewhere in between the three study programmes, a user who is completely unaware of their interests, a user who has a very specific career in mind, and a user who has interests that do not match any of the study programmes. Each of the systems will be tested while keeping these scenarios in mind, answering the questions in a way one might expect the users in these scenarios to answer them.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Questionnaire for design validation

The questionnaire was responded to by ten participants, mostly students who responded to the profiling questionnaire discussed in section 3.1.1. No further information on the participants was collected. The discussion of this questionnaire’s results will be based on the assumption that the participants’ profile matches the profile of the participants in the profiling questionnaire. Refer to the limitations (section 6.2) for a discussion of the implications should this assumption prove incorrect³.

Figure 5.12 shows the evaluations of the systems on each of the four previously discussed criteria. The evaluations were found by averaging participants’ evaluations of the relevant statements, where the rating of negative statements (e.g. “The system’s result does not appear trustworthy”) was inverted so that 5 becomes 1, 4 becomes 2, etc. Notable is that the decision tree performs exceptionally well on usability, with 100% of the participants rating a 5 on all relevant statements. The *overall evaluation*, found by averaging the evaluations of the four criteria, is *3.31 for the decision tree*, *3.89 for PAW-PAW* and *3.76 for the conversational system*.

Figure 5.13 shows which of the three systems participants preferred. The figure shows the answers to the question “Which system are you most likely to use when selecting a study programme?”, 60% of the participants selected PAW-PAW, 30% selected the conversational system and 10% selected the decision tree. The participant who selected the decision tree did so because they found it easy to use and understand. The participants who preferred the conversational system did so because they liked the conversational nature of the interactions and the amount of

³The files containing the raw results are stored following the data management plan of the University of Amsterdam.

Figure 5.12: The average evaluation of each system on four criteria on a five-point Likert scale. *Usability* shows how easy-to-use participants found the system, *answer quality* shows if participants felt like they could provide sufficient information on their preferences, *confidence* shows the confidence users have in the system's result and *time saving* shows to what extent each system is perceived as time-saving by the participants.

Figure 5.13: The percentage of respondents that selected each system as their answer to the question “Which system are you most likely to use during study programme selection?”

detail they could provide in their answers to the system’s questions. Participants who preferred PAW-PAW explained that they liked the nuance they could give to their answers without having to “create something”. Furthermore, they stated that the system encouraged them to think critically about their answers, and that they preferred the presentation of the result as a ranking of study programmes as opposed to a single study programme.

When asked for potential improvements of the systems, participants provided insightful feedback. Six students responded to the question in which they were asked what they would change about the decision tree. Three of those students said that the *decision tree should have been more extensive*, and two students said they would have liked to see a visualization of the tree. Two students indicated that they think the system would be more effective if it allowed more nuanced answers by providing more than two options for each question or asking more follow-up questions. Of the five students who suggested improvements for PAW-PAW, two indicated that they would have liked more nuanced criteria (e.g. splitting *mathematics* into sub-fields such as statistics or linear algebra). Two students found PAW-PAW to be overwhelming, one of which stated that rating relative importance on an eight point scale was unintuitive. One student suggested a countdown in the GUI, showing the number of questions not yet answered. The *conversational system had a tendency to go off-topic* according to one participant. Another participant indicated that the *conversational system often hallucinated incorrect information about the study programmes*. One participant suggested a minor improvement in the GUI, and one suggested instructing the system to provide examples of possible answers to its questions. Two students indicated that the system was often *slow to respond, and occasionally stopped responding altogether*. This has been found to be a problem with OpenAI’s API; if OpenAI’s servers are too busy, the API becomes slow or unresponsive, sometimes causing the `openai` Python library to throw an exception.

Two participants provided more general remarks on the three systems’ applicability in the study programme dilemma. Both indicated that *each system would be useful in different phases of the process*. One participant stated that the conversational system would be useful to prospective

students who are not yet aware of their criteria, as it could help them understand what aspects of the field intersect with their interests. This participant indicated that PAW-PAW would be more useful to prospective students who know their criteria but are still evaluating what study programmes fit those criteria. The other participant stated they would use the decision tree to verify their decision after they have already selected a study programme, use PAW-PAW to find the differences between the study programmes and how they match their criteria, and would use the conversational system to gather information on each study programme.

5.3.2 Self-evaluation

The decision tree performs well on all three best-case scenarios. A student who is a perfect fit for B.Sc. Informatica will get B.Sc. Informatica as a result, and the same applies to the other two study programmes. The rigidity and the binary nature of the decision tree become more problematic in the edge case of a student who does not know what their interests are; this student would likely be unable to answer some questions, e.g. “Do you want to learn about human intelligence or human-technology interaction?” Other difficulties may arise when a student knows the type of career they aspire, but do not know the types of subjects they would have to study for such a career. Since the decision tree’s design was focused primarily on the study programmes themselves, this student would be unable to answer the questions they are asked. Finally, the student whose interests align with none of the study programmes will never get a correct result, since the tree never results in anything other than the study programmes at CoI.

PAW-PAW performs similarly for the best-case scenarios. Students who appear to be a perfect fit are matched to the correct study programmes. The edge cases, however, are more interesting. If all criteria are selected, and all comparisons are evaluated as “equally important”, PAW-PAW will return the following ranking:

1. B.Sc. Informatiekunde (score: 19),
2. B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie (score: 17),
3. B.Sc. Informatica (score: 15).

Since PAW-PAW was not designed with career prospects in mind, this system is also unable to provide assistance to students who have specific career aspirations. Furthermore, a student who is unsure what their criteria for a study programme are would have difficulty answering the questions provided by this system, since they are not only required to select their criteria, but also to evaluate their relative importance. A student with interests that do not align in any way with one of the three study programmes will be presented with a ranking of the three anyway, which may lead to confusion. Displaying the score of each study programme does, however, indicate whether it is worth investigating one of the study programmes further. This indication could be more effective if the maximum score of each of the study programmes would be displayed.

The conversational system performs less consistently than the other two methods. PAW-PAW and the decision tree have deterministic outcomes; GPT 3.5 does not. When the system was told that the user is interested in mathematics, programming, software design and system architecture, it responded that both Informatica and Kunstmatige Intelligentie might be a fit. It took until the user stated that they were not interested in using large amounts of data for the system to advise looking into B.Sc. Informatica. In another conversation, where the user gave the same information, the system did not leap to conclusions in the second message. Instead, it asked several follow-up questions, ultimately leading to the conclusion that an interest in mathematics, programming in C, system architecture and the connection between hardware and software might be a good fit for Informatica and Kunstmatige Intelligentie. This appears to indicate a bias towards B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie; these subjects are central in B.Sc. Informatica, and not nearly as common in B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie.

In a different conversation, a user with an interest in big data, business, programming and human-technology interaction also received the advice to look into B.Sc. Informatica and B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie. This result is surprising; while both business and human-technology interaction are main themes in B.Sc. Informatiekunde, they are quite uncommon in the other

two study programmes. A student with arts and culture as its main interests is first advised to look into B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie; according to the system, this study programme includes courses on creating generative art by using AI, which is not true (*Informatiekunde - Studiegids 2022 - 2023* 2022). These findings expose an important issue with the conversational system; it shows a tendency to generate information that is not based on reality.

Discussion

6.1 Providing effective decision support

Our hypothesis regarding the performance of the decision tree appears to be *confirmed* by the results presented in the previous chapter. Its rigid and binary nature contribute to a high performance on usability, and its deterministic structure leads to consistent results. However, participants found that this rigidity made it difficult to provide enough detail and nuance in their answers, which had a negative effect on the confidence in its outcome and the effectiveness of the support it provided.

The hypothesis with regard to modifying AHP is *partially confirmed*. Modifying AHP to create PAW-PAW has proven to be a viable method to support students during the study program selection process, with 60% of participants preferring it over the other two methods. Although the quality of the data used to profile current students could be improved (see section 6.3), the data collected in this study appears to provide a satisfactory foundation for decision support. The suspicion that PAW-PAW's consistency check would be perceived as tedious, however, can not be confirmed; none of the participants mentioned this feature.

The conversational system was hypothesized to provide effective support by allowing personalization and being able to answer the user's questions. This can be *confirmed to some degree*; participants indicated that they liked the amount of detail they could provide when describing their interests, and although participants were, on average, not as confident in its result as they were in PAW-PAW's result, its rating for time-saving was on par with PAW-PAW's. The experiment, however, did also expose several issues with the system's applicability in a DSS. As some participants noted, the system was occasionally slow to respond, and in some cases became unresponsive. This could negatively impact the effectiveness of the decision support, especially if the conversation history is not stored, forcing users to start over. Furthermore, the system's tendency to hallucinate (i.e. generate information that is not based on real or accurate knowledge) indicates that this technology may not yet be suited to help people make decisions that could profoundly impact their lives.

6.1.1 Comparing the decision support methods

The results of the experiments appear to indicate that PAW-PAW is the most successful of the three systems at providing decision support. It scores highest of the three on *confidence* and *time saving*, and is a close second on *answer quality*. The only criterion on which it is greatly outperformed by another system is *usability*. Furthermore, 60% of participants preferred PAW-PAW over the other systems, which is twice as many as the second most popular system, the conversational system, at 30%. The answer to this thesis' research question, however, is more nuanced than that.

It is important to realize that *each system has its drawbacks and benefits*, and fits into the study programme selection process differently. There is an important trade-off between *usability* and *answer quality*; as the amount of nuance and detail the user can provide to the system

increases, so does the complexity of the interactions. Choosing between two options requires less work than providing a rating on an eight-point scale, and requires less thought than typing out a message in which one describes their own interests. To the participant who preferred the decision tree, the better usability was worth its trade-off with the amount of nuance they could provide in their answers. Other participants preferred sacrificing some usability in favour of the ability to nuance their answers.

The trade-off between usability and answer quality is not the only one; *a systems' performance on each criterion is connected to its performance on the other criteria* in one way or another, and the ways in which they are connected vary per participant. This is demonstrated by participants' responses to the questionnaire. One participant preferred the conversational system because, according to them, the amount of detail they could provide increased their confidence in the outcome, which increased the probability that they would use the system's result in their selection process. This, in turn, increased the probability that using the system would save them time. This contrasts with another participant, who indicated that the amount of detail they could provide in PAW-PAW caused them to question the system's result.

Although several participants indicated that both the decision tree's and PAW-PAW's performance might be improved by using more specific criteria, one should be careful when increasing the amount of detail in the criteria. For example, splitting machine learning or mathematics into sub-categories would allow users to be more specific when describing their interests, presumably increasing the precision of the decision support, however, this may cause difficulty for the less initiated users. High school students, for example, may not be aware of the distinction between statistical mathematics and linear algebra. A system that uses this distinction may be more confusing than helpful to them.

6.1.2 GPT's performance now and in the future

While the conversational system appears to be a promising method to assist students in selecting a study program, its performance is still lacking in several key areas. The system being slow to respond and occasionally becoming unresponsive has a negative impact on its usability, which could be detrimental to the effectiveness of the decision support. Furthermore, the system appears to have a bias towards B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie and to a lesser degree B.Sc. Informatica. Combined with the system's tendency to hallucinate, this could lead to incorrect advice, which could negatively impact the desirability of the outcome of decisions made using this system.

It is important to note that the technology behind the conversational system, the GPT language model, is quite new and is still undergoing rapid development. In March, GPT version 4 was released. GPT 4 outperforms the model that was used in the conversational system, GPT 3.5, on most aspects of its functionality; although it is slower to respond, GPT 4 has a better understanding of language and has a lower probability of hallucinating information (OpenAI 2023). As the technology continues to improve in the near future, its capability to provide accurate decision support in the study programme selection process may improve drastically; using new developments in this technology to provide assistance in the study program dilemma is likely a valuable area for future research.

6.1.3 Answering the research question

This thesis' research question, as introduced in section 1.2, is **“How can we support students in their decision on which study program to enrol in?”** There is no unambiguous answer to this question, as each of the systems studied in this thesis has its place in the study program selection process. The success of these decision support systems is influenced by several factors, most importantly the student's decision-making style, and how far into the study program selection process the student is. **This indicates that the best answer to this question is not to select one method, but to combine several methods into one system.**

6.2 Limitations

This study has some limitations. The two main categories are limitations of the method used to profile current students and limitations of the method used to verify the decision support system's design. The limitations of the profiling method include the qualitative nature of the method and potential issues with the incorporation of the course catalogues. The design's limitations include issues with OpenAI's API, issues with the design of the decision tree and the conversational system, and the potential for improvement in the criteria used to provide decision support.

There are several potential issues with the method used to profile current students at CoI. Since no data on these students' interests and motivations were available prior to this study, the topics that students are interested in were relatively unknown. To prevent nudging students toward our own potential prejudices about the study programmes, the questionnaire contained open questions, to which students responded in free text. For these data to be analysed, the additional step of labelling the data was required. Introducing this step increases the potential for human error. Furthermore, the open nature of the questions might lead students to provide only low-hanging fruit in their responses; some important subjects might be underexposed because they were not of importance in the more recent courses, or because they are more abstract than other subjects. This is partially demonstrated by the responses to the question: "What is your study programme's least important subject?" The responses to this question included mostly subjects from courses that were active at the time the students received the questionnaire. Finally, when incorporating the course catalogues in the students' profiles, teachers at the programs should have been asked to verify the labels used to describe their courses. This could have increased the precision of the profiles, as such increasing the quality of the decision support.

Some other issues may be present in the design of the three systems. The better part of this study was working towards PAW-PAW's design, while significantly less time was spent on designing the decision tree and the conversational system. This has several implications, the most important of which is a potential difference in design quality between the three methods compared in this study. When asked what they would change about the decision tree, four of the ten participants commented that it should have been more extensive. Furthermore, two respondent highlighted the need for improving the design of the decision tree and PAW-PAW by incorporating more nuanced criteria, such as distinguishing between various sub-fields within mathematics. The conversational system's performance might have been improved by spending more time on prompt engineering. Finally, there is the issue of PAW-PAW ranking B.Sc. Informatiekunde highest if all criteria are evaluated equal. This problem is unfortunately not solvable by normalizing the scores of each study program; this could cause the ratios of the scores of all study program on one criterium to shift, changing how well the individual scores reflect reality.

The sample of participants who responded to the final questionnaire may pose a problem as well. A large gap in the questionnaire is that no information on these participants' backgrounds was collected. As such, it is impossible to determine whether the sample is representative of the target audience. Furthermore, the questionnaire was sent to current students at CoI, while the intended end-users of the system are high school students. Finally, a larger sample size could be desirable.

The results of the questionnaire for DSS evaluation were discussed under the assumption that most participants were students at CoI. If this assumption turns out to be incorrect, it would have some implications. First, the considerations for the specificity of the criteria used in the systems would change; if it was a high school student who requested differentiating between several types of mathematics, it would indicate that this level of detail could be desirable. Furthermore, the results of the questionnaire are likely to be relatively precise if most participants are first year students, as they went through the study program selection process quite recently. However, if most participants are third year students, their experience with the programmes might affect their responses, resulting in less accurate results.

The final issue is that it is unknown whether the case study in this thesis is applicable to other cases. Students who are considering enrolling into CoI might have a different selection process from others. For example, these students might be more likely to adopt a systematic strategy when selecting a study programme. Furthermore, it can be suspected that these students have a relatively high degree of computer literacy, which might increase the probability that they would

be able to effectively use decision support systems.

6.3 Improvements

When conducting follow-up research, these limitations should be taken into account. This section suggests methods to improve each of the previously discussed limitations. When implemented, these improvements may result in more precise and more reliable results, thus potentially increasing the effectiveness of decision support provided in the future.

First, the issues with the questionnaire that was used to profile students can be resolved by supplementing the results of this thesis' qualitative study by performing a quantitative study. In this new study, students should be asked to rate the relative importance of subjects and academic interests on a Likert scale. If the list of subjects from this thesis' results is supplemented with subjects taken from the course catalogue, this more quantitative approach could prevent the issue where students forget to mention certain subjects. Furthermore, it may decrease the impact of the recency effect where mentions of current courses were disproportionately common. The method described in this paragraph may yield more nuanced criteria and lead to a more precise profile of current students, thus improving the results' potential to be used to provide precise decision support.

Second, when replicating this study, more time should be spent on designing the decision tree and the conversational system. The decision tree should be more extensive than the one used in this study, and ask more nuanced questions to the user. The conversational system could be improved by spending more time on prompt engineering. Furthermore, a way to prevent the conversational system from becoming unresponsive if the OpenAI API is experiencing issues is desirable. A simple way to do this would be to alert the user when an issue with the API is detected, giving them the option to resubmit their message. These improvements, when combined with a larger number of participants, should increase the reliability of the study's results.

Finally, the knowledge on participants' profile should be improved. In replications or continuations of this study, verifying whether the sample on which the conclusions are based is representative of the target group would improve the precision of the conclusions.

Conclusions

This thesis aimed to interpret the dropout rates at University of Amsterdam's College of Informatics and propose a possible method to decrease the number of dropouts. This can be achieved by helping students to enrol in a study program that matches their expectations. To do so, a decision support system for precisely selecting a study program at the College of Informatics is designed. The design was implemented in a prototype and verified by having participants evaluate several implementations of decision support systems, and comparing the results.

The reviewed literature indicates that the study program selection process fits into the *bounded rationality* model, meaning that the information available to the decision-maker is imperfect or otherwise incomplete. Since most decision-making methods assume that the decision-maker has sufficient information available to them, many are not applicable in the scenario of selecting a study program. Furthermore, previous research into decision support systems in education tends to focus on education management scenarios. The studies that do focus on the study program dilemma often only verify feasibility of implementation or omit the most common reasons to enrol in a study programme.

Students at the College of Informatics provided insights into their experiences at their study programmes and their decision-making process, resulting in a profile for each of the study programmes at the College of Informatics and a model of the study programme selection process. The profiles were used to find several distinguishing characteristics which could be used to help prospective students choose one of the programs. The model of the decision-making process showed that the process consists of several phases, and that the way in which support could be provided differs in each phase.

PAW-PAW was introduced as a method that could assist students in their decision without requiring information that is not available to them, while using the same criteria that prospective students use when choosing a study programme. PAW-PAW combines the weighting method of the Analytical Hierarchy Process with the weighted sum method, and uses the profiles of students at the College of Informatics to create a personalized ranking of study programmes for prospective students.

PAW-PAW was evaluated by participants to be more effective at providing decision support than a decision tree and a GPT-based conversational system; although it was outperformed by both the decision tree and the conversational system on usability, it was rated second most effective at allowing the user to provide detailed information on their preferences, and outperformed the other two systems on both the users' confidence in the results and the likelihood that it would save users time when being used in the study programme selection process. Furthermore, 60% of the participants selected PAW-PAW as the system they would most likely want to use when selecting a study programme. Participants indicated that the decision tree did not allow for enough nuance in the answers they could provide, and that the conversational system too often strayed off-topic or generated incorrect information.

Although these results seem to indicate PAW-PAW as the best of the three methods to provide decision support, the more general comments left by the participants nuance this answer. Several participants indicated that each system has its benefits and its drawbacks, and that each

system would fit into the study program selection process differently; the effectiveness of each system depends on how well the user knows their own preferences. Furthermore, users may have varying decision-making styles, which could affect the effectiveness of each system differently. **In conclusion: providing effective decision support to students who are selecting a study program is not achieved by some “one method fits all” solution; a combination of decision support methods is desirable.**

Future work

This study has revealed several areas that might prove valuable subjects for future research. Some areas pertain

The first subject for future research is ELECTRE, one of the decision-making methods that was discussed in the theoretical background, but not used thereafter. Although ELECTRE has shown promise in study program selection, it was disregarded in this thesis under the assumption that its pair-wise comparisons of alternatives were difficult to perform for prospective students. This assumption was based on the idea that comparing alternatives on several criteria requires information that is not yet available to prospective students. However, the previously found applicability of ELECTRE in the study program dilemma suggests that verifying this assumption could prove valuable.

The second subject is applying GPT 4 or possible future versions of the model to provide decision support for study program selection. Since the model is still being rapidly developed, its effectiveness at providing decision support might improve drastically in the near future. If its tendencies to hallucinate incorrect information and to become unresponsive become less prevalent, it might prove a very effective decision support method.

The third area to look into is applying machine learning to profile current students and match prospective students to one of the study programs. As discussed in section 2.2.3, machine learning has proven an effective method to predict students' academic performance. This suggests that using a machine learning algorithm to classify students into the study programs that best fit their profile could be an effective method to help prospective students decide in which program to enrol.

A fourth recommendation for future work is to look into the career prospects of each study programme. Career prospects and expected salary are among the most commonly used criteria for study program selection. In this study, these criteria were mostly disregarded, as there was not enough time to collect the data needed to incorporate this in the decision support. The results of the questionnaire used to profile students at the College of Informatics, however, does confirm that these criteria are also common for this thesis' target groups, indicating that accurate information on career prospects might help students precisely select a study programme.

Finally, as concluded previously, designing a system that combines several decision support methods is a largely unexplored area that might yield promising results. One example of how one might do this, is by creating a system that determines what phase of the study program selection process the user is currently in, and what their decision-making style is. This system could then direct the user to the decision support system that best suits their needs, improving the effectiveness of the support provided by the system.

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Questionnaire to Profile Current Students

A.1 *Algemene vragen*

- Welke opleiding doe je?
- In welk jaar ben je met die opleiding begonnen?
- Wat is het hoogste opleidingsniveau dat je behaald hebt voordat je je huidige opleiding startte?
- Ben je vóór je huidige opleiding ingeschreven geweest bij een andere opleiding?
- Zo ja, waarom ben je van opleiding gewisseld? (laat dit veld leeg als je op de vorige vraag "nee" geantwoord hebt)
- De volgende vraag hoef je alleen in te vullen als je huidige opleiding B.Sc. Informatica, B.Sc. Informatiekunde of B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie is. Waarom heb je niet voor een van de andere twee bovengenoemde opleidingen gekozen?
- Heb je getwijfeld tussen verschillende bacheloropleidingen?
- Zo ja, tussen welke opleidingen twijfelde je, en waarom heb je je uiteindelijke keuze gemaakt?
- Als je jouw opleiding in kernwoorden zou moeten omschrijven, welke zou je dan gebruiken? Geef ze door komma's gescheiden ("kernwoord 1, kernwoord 2, ...")
- Als je jouw interesses in kernwoorden zou moeten omschrijven, welke zou je dan gebruiken? Geef ze in hetzelfde format als de vraag hiervoor.

A.2 *Informatievoorzieningen*

- Welke informatievoorziening(en) heb je gebruikt bij het kiezen van je opleiding?
- Hoe tevreden ben je over de informatievoorzieningen die je gebruikt hebt?
- Toelichting vorig antwoord
- Welke informatie miste je bij het maken van je keuze?

A.3 *Verwachtingen*

- Waarom heb je je huidige opleiding gekozen?
- Deze vraag hoef je alleen in te vullen als je een van de bacheloropleidingen voor informatiewetenschappen volgt of gevolgd hebt. Voldoet of voldeed deze opleiding aan de verwachtingen die je er van tevoren van had?
- Toelichting vorig antwoord
- Wat is voor jou het belangrijkste onderwerp binnen je opleiding?
- Wat is voor jou het minst belangrijke onderwerp binnen je opleiding?

A.4 *Ruimte voor opmerkingen en feedback*

- Ruimte voor verdere opmerkingen
- Mogen we contact met je opnemen voor verdere vragen? Zo ja, hoe kunnen we je bereiken?

Questionnaire on the Decision-making Process

- Welke van deze opleidingen heb je overwogen naast Informatica?
- In hoeverre zijn de volgende stellingen op jou van toepassing? 1 (helemaal niet), 2, 3, 4, 5 (helemaal)
 - Ik vond het moeilijk om een opleiding te kiezen.
 - Ik heb mijn keuze vooral op gevoel of intuïtie gemaakt.
 - Het type baan dat je kan krijgen met een studie heeft niet meegewogen in mijn keuze.
 - Ik heb me ingeschreven bij de eerste opleiding die me leuk leek
 - Voor mijn studiekeuze is het belangrijk dat een vakgebied iets bijdraagt aan de maatschappij.
 - Wat mijn ouders/verzorgers van de opleidingen vonden woog mee in mijn studiekeuze.
 - Wat mijn vrienden vonden was onbelangrijk in mijn studiekeuze.
 - Ik heb mijn studiekeuze deels gebaseerd op cijfers die ik voor verwante vakken haalde op school.
 - Het idee dat ik met een studie later veel geld kan verdienen is niet belangrijk voor mijn keuze.
 - Ik weet precies welke vakken ik in mijn studie ga krijgen, en wat die vakken inhouden.
 - Ik had een systematische aanpak bij het kiezen van een studie.
- Waar heb je de informatie die je nodig had voor je studiekeuze vandaan gehaald?
- Hoe tevreden ben je over de beschikbaarheid van de informatie die je nodig had voor je studiekeuze?
- Toelichting vorige vraag
- Hebben wij je al geïnterviewd tijdens de matching?
- Wil je verder nog iets kwijt over je studiekeuze bij de UvA?

Questionnaire for design validation

- Decision tree; in hoeverre zijn de volgende stellingen bij jou van toepassing? 1 (helemaal niet) - 5 (helemaal)
 - De decision tree was makkelijk te gebruiken.
 - De decision tree gaf me voldoende de mogelijkheid om mijn antwoorden te nuanceren.
 - Het resultaat van de decision tree komt onbetrouwbaar over.
 - Als ik de decision tree tijdens mijn studiekeuze zou gebruiken, zou het me geen tijd besparen.
 - De decision tree laat me kritisch over mijn antwoorden nadenken.
 - Ik kon in de decision tree niet genoeg details over mijn interesses opgeven.
 - De decision tree maakt me zekerder over mijn keuze.
 - Ik geloof niet dat het resultaat van de decision tree klopt.
 - Ik begreep gelijk hoe ik dit systeem moest gebruiken
- PAW-PAW; in hoeverre zijn de volgende stellingen bij jou van toepassing? 1 (helemaal niet) - 5 (helemaal)
 - PAW-PAW was makkelijk te gebruiken.
 - PAW-PAW gaf me voldoende de mogelijkheid om mijn antwoorden te nuanceren.
 - Het resultaat van PAW-PAW komt onbetrouwbaar over.
 - Als ik PAW-PAW tijdens mijn studiekeuze zou gebruiken, zou het me geen tijd besparen.
 - PAW-PAW laat me kritisch over mijn antwoorden nadenken.
 - Ik kon in PAW-PAW niet genoeg details over mijn interesses opgeven.
 - PAW-PAW maakt me zekerder over mijn keuze.
 - Ik geloof niet dat het resultaat van PAW-PAW klopt.
 - Ik begreep gelijk hoe ik dit systeem moest gebruiken
- Conversationeel systeem; in hoeverre zijn de volgende stellingen bij jou van toepassing? 1 (helemaal niet) - 5 (helemaal)
 - Het conversationele systeem was makkelijk te gebruiken.
 - Het conversationele systeem gaf me voldoende de mogelijkheid om mijn antwoorden te nuanceren.
 - Het resultaat van het conversationele systeem komt onbetrouwbaar over.

- Als ik het conversationele systeem tijdens mijn studiekeuze zou gebruiken, zou het me geen tijd besparen.
- het conversationele systeem laat me kritisch over mijn antwoorden nadenken.
- Ik kon in het conversationele systeem niet genoeg details over mijn interesses opgeven.
- Het conversationele systeem maakt me zekerder over mijn keuze.
- Ik geloof niet dat het resultaat van het conversationele systeem klopt.
- Ik begreep gelijk hoe ik dit systeem moest gebruiken

Decision tree design

The design of the decision tree is shown in figure D.1.

Figure D.1: The design of the decision tree used in the experiment.

Conversational system prompt

Je bent een chatsysteem voor hulp bij het kiezen van een studie binnen de informatiewetenschappen aan de Universiteit van Amsterdam. De mogelijke studies zijn B.Sc. Informatica, B.Sc. Informatiekunde en B.Sc. Kunstmatige Intelligentie. Hieronder staan bij de drie opleidingen steeds 10 onderwerpen met daar achter tussen haakjes een getal dat aangeeft hoe belangrijk dat onderwerp is binnen de opleiding. Hierbij is de maximale score 100.

Kunstmatige Intelligentie scoort als volgt: wiskunde (37.7), data science (4.2), organisatiekunde (0), machine learning (30.5), mens (2.1), programmeren (61.7), theorie (8.5), psychologie (22.4), multidisciplinair (6.8), bedrijfskunde (0).

Informatica scoort als volgt: wiskunde (40.6), data science (8.3), organisatiekunde (0), machine learning (4.3), mens (0), programmeren (66.8), theorie (27.7), psychologie (0), multidisciplinair (1.7), bedrijfskunde (0).

Informatiekunde scoort als volgt: wiskunde (2), data science (36), organisatiekunde (30), machine learning (7), mens (26), programmeren (41), theorie (2), psychologie (7), multidisciplinair (23), bedrijfskunde (20).

Stel de gebruiker minstens 3 keer een vervolgvraag, in 3 aparte berichten; maximaal 1 vraag per bericht. Houd de berichten kort. Noem de scores niet expliciet. Je geeft de gebruiker op zijn vroegst in het achtste bericht een advies.